

Different Types and Aspects of Magic Squares of Order 16

The whole work as pdf files is available at author's sites:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=16911>

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Abstract

*This work summarizes author's previous works on magic squares of order 16. It brings different types of magic square such as **block-wise, single-digit bordered, double-digit bordered, cornered, designs, styles, etc.** In terms of aspects, we have considered the idea of **Pythagorean triples, upside-down, mirror-looking, water reflection, perfect square sum entries, Latin square distributions, algebraic magic squares, etc.***

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1 Introduction

In the previous works [19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25], the author worked with **block-wise** constructions of magic squares. The work is from the orders 8 to 45. In each case, all the possibilities are considered. These possibilities are based on divisions of magic squares. The magic sums of order n of consecutive numbers from 1 to n^2 is given by

$$S_{n \times n} := \frac{n \times (1 + n^2)}{2}, n \geq 3. \quad (1)$$

This formula is applied to all order magic squares. Based on this formula we shall bring **blocks** for the **block-wise** magic squares. That is, whenever is possible, we shall try to bring blocks of equal sum magic squares. In some cases, they are **magic, semi-magic, pandiagonal**, etc. When the question come to **bimagic** squares, in some cases, we have **semi-bimagic** squares.

On the other hand the idea of **bordered** magic squares is well explained in the work by H.White [4, 5]. Few results in this direction can be seen in author's work [26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31]. In some case, the magic rectangles are also used to write it in different styles. Most of the author's work on magic squares is summarized below in details according to topic:

1. *Digital Fonts: Upside-down and Mirror Looking.*
2. *Two Digits Universal Magic Squares.*
3. *Different Digits Magic Squares.*
4. *Pythagorean Triples Magic Squares.*
5. *Block-Wise Magic Squares.*
6. *Selfie and Palindromic Type Magic Squares.*
7. *Block Bordered Magic Squares.*
8. *Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares.*
9. *Magic Crosses, Letters and Numbers.*
10. *Cornered Magic Squares.*
11. *Single-Digit Bordered Magic Squares.*
12. *Double-Digit Bordered Magic Squares.*
13. *Multiple-Digit Bordered Magic Squares.*
14. *Striped Magic Squares.*
15. *Upside-down and Mirror Looking.*
16. *Water reflection Magic Squares.*

17. *Algebraic Maic Squares.*

The aim of this work is to write magic squares of order 16 in different ways and styles using the aspects of **blocks**, **bordered**, **block-bordered** and **magic rectangles**, **corner-type**, **single-digit**, **double-digit**, etc.

More details on these works on **magic squares** can be seen in author's web-sites:

(i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>

(ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>

2 Different Types of Magic Squares

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 16 is given by

$$S_{16 \times 16} := \frac{16 \times (1 + 16^2)}{2} = 2056.$$

We can write, $16 := 4^2 = 4 \times 4$. This gives the possibility of blocks of order 4 and 8. Let's see division of 2056 by 4 and 2:

$$(i) \quad \frac{2056}{4} = 514 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 4;}$$
$$(ii) \quad \frac{2056}{2} = 1024 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 8.}$$

Below are few examples of different types of magic squares of order 16.

2.1 Block-Wise Magic Squares

Example 2.1.

	pan	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056
2056	7	252	1	254	15	244	9	246	23	236	17	238	31	228	25	230	2056
2056	2	253	8	251	10	245	16	243	18	237	24	235	26	229	32	227	2056
2056	256	3	250	5	248	11	242	13	240	19	234	21	232	27	226	29	2056
2056	249	6	255	4	241	14	247	12	233	22	239	20	225	30	231	28	2056
2056	39	220	33	222	47	212	41	214	55	204	49	206	63	196	57	198	2056
2056	34	221	40	219	42	213	48	211	50	205	56	203	58	197	64	195	2056
2056	224	35	218	37	216	43	210	45	208	51	202	53	200	59	194	61	2056
2056	217	38	223	36	209	46	215	44	201	54	207	52	193	62	199	60	2056
2056	71	188	65	190	79	180	73	182	87	172	81	174	95	164	89	166	2056
2056	66	189	72	187	74	181	80	179	82	173	88	171	90	165	96	163	2056
2056	192	67	186	69	184	75	178	77	176	83	170	85	168	91	162	93	2056
2056	185	70	191	68	177	78	183	76	169	86	175	84	161	94	167	92	2056
2056	103	156	97	158	111	148	105	150	119	140	113	142	127	132	121	134	2056
2056	98	157	104	155	106	149	112	147	114	141	120	139	122	133	128	131	2056
2056	160	99	154	101	152	107	146	109	144	115	138	117	136	123	130	125	2056
	153	102	159	100	145	110	151	108	137	118	143	116	129	126	135	124	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

It is a block-wise *pandiagonal* magic square of order 16 with equal sums *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 4.

Example 2.2.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/							https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/							©IJT	2056
8	2	254	256	243	13	245	7	40	34	222	224	211	45	213	39	2056
5	238	236	17	242	18	20	252	37	206	204	49	210	50	52	220	2056
6	16	31	228	25	230	241	251	38	48	63	196	57	198	209	219	2056
11	22	26	229	32	227	235	246	43	54	58	197	64	195	203	214	2056
253	24	232	27	226	29	233	4	221	56	200	59	194	61	201	36	2056
248	234	225	30	231	28	23	9	216	202	193	62	199	60	55	41	2056
247	237	21	240	15	239	19	10	215	205	53	208	47	207	51	42	2056
250	255	3	1	14	244	12	249	218	223	35	33	46	212	44	217	2056
104	98	158	160	147	109	149	103	72	66	190	192	179	77	181	71	2056
101	142	140	113	146	114	116	156	69	174	172	81	178	82	84	188	2056
102	112	127	132	121	134	145	155	70	80	95	164	89	166	177	187	2056
107	118	122	133	128	131	139	150	75	86	90	165	96	163	171	182	2056
157	120	136	123	130	125	137	100	189	88	168	91	162	93	169	68	2056
152	138	129	126	135	124	119	105	184	170	161	94	167	92	87	73	2056
151	141	117	144	111	143	115	106	183	173	85	176	79	175	83	74	2056
154	159	99	97	110	148	108	153	186	191	67	65	78	180	76	185	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

It is a **block-wise** magic square of order 16, where the blocks are single-digit bordered magic squares of order 8.

For more details refer author's work [20, 22].

2.2 Block-Wise Bimagic Square

Example 2.3.

Bimagic Square of Order 16x16. Magic Squares of Order 4 are of Equal Magic Sums																	
mgc																351576	
mgc	1476	2056	2764	2056	1356	2056	2628	2056	1612	2056	2372	2056	1732	2056	2508	2056	
1	154	239	120	23	144	249	98	44	179	198	93	62	165	212	75	2056	351576
232	127	10	145	242	105	32	135	205	86	35	188	219	68	53	174	2056	351576
122	225	152	15	112	247	130	25	83	204	189	38	69	222	171	52	2056	351576
159	8	113	234	137	18	103	256	182	45	92	195	164	59	78	213	2056	351576
46	181	196	91	60	163	214	77	7	160	233	114	17	138	255	104	2056	351576
203	84	37	190	221	70	51	172	226	121	16	151	248	111	26	129	2056	351576
85	206	187	36	67	220	173	54	128	231	146	9	106	241	136	31	2056	351576
180	43	94	197	166	61	76	211	153	2	119	240	143	24	97	250	2056	351576
55	176	217	66	33	186	207	88	30	133	244	107	12	147	230	125	2056	351576
210	73	64	167	200	95	42	177	251	100	21	142	237	118	3	156	2056	351576
80	215	162	57	90	193	184	47	101	254	139	20	115	236	157	6	2056	351576
169	50	71	224	191	40	81	202	132	27	110	245	150	13	124	227	2056	351576
28	131	246	109	14	149	228	123	49	170	223	72	39	192	201	82	2056	351576
253	102	19	140	235	116	5	158	216	79	58	161	194	89	48	183	2056	351576
99	252	141	22	117	238	155	4	74	209	168	63	96	199	178	41	2056	351576
134	29	108	243	148	11	126	229	175	56	65	218	185	34	87	208	2056	351576
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056
351576	351576	351576	351576	351576	351576	351576	351576	351576	351576	351576	351576	351576	351576	351576	351576	351576	351576

It is a bimagic square of order 16. The blocks of order 4 are equal sums magic square of order 4.

For more details refer author's work [11]

2.3 Single-Digit Bordered Magic Squares

Example 2.4.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														2056	
241	228	230	232	251	253	255	30	28	26	24	7	5	3	1	242	2056
23	213	202	204	206	222	224	56	54	52	50	36	34	32	214	234	2056
21	49	189	180	182	197	199	78	76	74	61	59	57	190	208	236	2056
18	47	73	169	162	164	176	96	94	92	82	80	170	184	210	239	2056
17	45	70	91	153	148	159	110	108	99	97	154	166	187	212	240	2056
12	41	69	89	106	141	138	120	118	112	142	151	168	188	216	245	2056
10	39	64	85	105	117	136	133	124	121	140	152	172	193	218	247	2056
8	31	62	79	100	111	122	123	134	135	146	157	178	195	226	249	2056
235	209	185	167	150	143	125	128	129	132	114	107	90	72	48	22	2056
237	211	186	171	155	144	131	130	127	126	113	102	86	71	46	20	2056
238	215	191	173	156	115	119	137	139	145	116	101	84	66	42	19	2056
243	217	192	174	103	109	98	147	149	158	160	104	83	65	40	14	2056
244	219	194	87	95	93	81	161	163	165	175	177	88	63	38	13	2056
246	220	67	77	75	60	58	179	181	183	196	198	200	68	37	11	2056
248	43	55	53	51	35	33	201	203	205	207	221	223	225	44	9	2056
15	29	27	25	6	4	2	227	229	231	233	250	252	254	256	16	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

It is a single-digit bordered magic square of order 16. Removing the higher borders still we are left with magic squares of lower orders, such as of orders 14, 12, 10,... etc. The internal block is a magic square of order 4.

For more details refer author's work [22, 24]

2.4 Embedded Single-Digit Bordered Magic Squares

Example 2.5.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														2056	
241	228	230	232	251	253	255	30	28	26	24	7	5	3	1	242	2056
23	213	202	204	206	222	224	56	54	52	50	36	34	32	214	234	2056
21	49	154	57	107	128	78	175	134	84	181	196	99	149	208	236	2056
18	47	59	106	153	174	127	80	180	133	86	101	148	195	210	239	2056
17	45	105	155	58	79	176	126	85	182	132	147	197	100	212	240	2056
12	41	187	90	140	143	93	190	113	63	160	169	72	122	216	245	2056
10	39	92	139	186	189	142	95	159	112	65	74	121	168	218	247	2056
8	31	138	188	91	94	191	141	64	161	111	120	170	73	226	249	2056
235	209	123	173	76	61	158	108	103	200	150	129	179	82	48	22	2056
237	211	77	124	171	156	109	62	198	151	104	83	130	177	46	20	2056
238	215	172	75	125	110	60	157	152	102	199	178	81	131	42	19	2056
243	217	144	194	97	88	185	135	70	167	117	114	164	67	40	14	2056
244	219	98	145	192	183	136	89	165	118	71	68	115	162	38	13	2056
246	220	193	96	146	137	87	184	119	69	166	163	66	116	37	11	2056
248	43	55	53	51	35	33	201	203	205	207	221	223	225	44	9	2056
15	29	27	25	6	4	2	227	229	231	233	250	252	254	256	16	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

It is a single-digit bordered magic square of order 16 embedded with a magic square of order 12 formed by equal sums semi-magic squares of order 3.

Example 2.6.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/												https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	©IJT	2056	
241	228	230	232	251	253	255	30	28	26	24	7	5	3	1	242	2056
23	213	202	204	206	222	224	56	54	52	50	36	34	32	214	234	2056
21	49	111	164	57	182	112	163	58	181	113	162	59	180	208	236	2056
18	47	74	165	128	147	73	166	127	148	72	167	126	149	210	239	2056
17	45	200	75	146	93	199	76	145	94	198	77	144	95	212	240	2056
12	41	129	110	183	92	130	109	184	91	131	108	185	90	216	245	2056
10	39	114	161	60	179	115	160	61	178	116	159	62	177	218	247	2056
8	31	71	168	125	150	70	169	124	151	69	170	123	152	226	249	2056
235	209	197	78	143	96	196	79	142	97	195	80	141	98	48	22	2056
237	211	132	107	186	89	133	106	187	88	134	105	188	87	46	20	2056
238	215	117	158	63	176	118	157	64	175	119	156	65	174	42	19	2056
243	217	68	171	122	153	67	172	121	154	66	173	120	155	40	14	2056
244	219	194	81	140	99	193	82	139	100	192	83	138	101	38	13	2056
246	220	135	104	189	86	136	103	190	85	137	102	191	84	37	11	2056
248	43	55	53	51	35	33	201	203	205	207	221	223	225	44	9	2056
15	29	27	25	6	4	2	227	229	231	233	250	252	254	256	16	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

It is a single-digit bordered magic square of order 16 embedded with a magic square of order 12 formed by equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 4.

Example 2.7.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												2056			
241	228	230	232	251	253	255	30	28	26	24	7	5	3	1	242	2056
23	213	202	204	206	222	224	56	54	52	50	36	34	32	214	234	2056
21	49	57	193	192	185	64	80	58	194	191	186	63	79	208	236	2056
18	47	176	88	168	89	97	153	175	87	167	90	98	154	210	239	2056
17	45	152	145	113	120	136	105	151	146	114	119	135	106	212	240	2056
12	41	128	112	137	144	121	129	127	111	138	143	122	130	216	245	2056
10	39	81	160	96	161	169	104	82	159	95	162	170	103	218	247	2056
8	31	177	73	65	72	184	200	178	74	66	71	183	199	226	249	2056
235	209	59	195	190	187	62	78	60	196	189	188	61	77	48	22	2056
237	211	174	86	166	91	99	155	173	85	165	92	100	156	46	20	2056
238	215	150	147	115	118	134	107	149	148	116	117	133	108	42	19	2056
243	217	126	110	139	142	123	131	125	109	140	141	124	132	40	14	2056
244	219	83	158	94	163	171	102	84	157	93	164	172	101	38	13	2056
246	220	179	75	67	70	182	198	180	76	68	69	181	197	37	11	2056
248	43	55	53	51	35	33	201	203	205	207	221	223	225	44	9	2056
15	29	27	25	6	4	2	227	229	231	233	250	252	254	256	16	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

It is a single-digit bordered magic square of order 16 embedded with a magic square of order 12 formed by equal sums magic squares of order 6.

Example 2.8.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														2056	
241	228	230	232	251	253	255	30	28	26	24	7	5	3	1	242	2056
23	213	202	204	206	222	224	56	54	52	50	36	34	32	214	234	2056
21	49	196	194	59	200	60	62	178	176	77	182	78	80	208	236	2056
18	47	58	73	186	67	188	199	76	91	168	85	170	181	210	239	2056
17	45	64	68	187	74	185	193	82	86	169	92	167	175	212	240	2056
12	41	66	190	69	184	71	191	84	172	87	166	89	173	216	245	2056
10	39	192	183	72	189	70	65	174	165	90	171	88	83	218	247	2056
8	31	195	63	198	57	197	61	177	81	180	75	179	79	226	249	2056
235	209	142	140	113	146	114	116	160	158	95	164	96	98	48	22	2056
237	211	112	127	132	121	134	145	94	109	150	103	152	163	46	20	2056
238	215	118	122	133	128	131	139	100	104	151	110	149	157	42	19	2056
243	217	120	136	123	130	125	137	102	154	105	148	107	155	40	14	2056
244	219	138	129	126	135	124	119	156	147	108	153	106	101	38	13	2056
246	220	141	117	144	111	143	115	159	99	162	93	161	97	37	11	2056
248	43	55	53	51	35	33	201	203	205	207	221	223	225	44	9	2056
15	29	27	25	6	4	2	227	229	231	233	250	252	254	256	16	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

It is a single-digit bordered magic square of order 16 embedded with a magic square of order 12 formed by four equal sums single-digit magic square of order 6

For more details refer author's work [24]

2.5 Cornered Magic Square

Example 2.9.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				©IJT		2056					
127	132	121	134	115	142	147	110	162	95	77	180	212	45	240	17	2056
122	133	128	131	141	116	108	149	85	172	190	67	55	202	10	247	2056
136	123	130	125	113	144	158	99	94	163	64	193	40	217	230	27	2056
129	126	135	124	119	138	155	102	167	90	60	197	38	219	236	21	2056
145	118	143	117	137	111	152	105	168	89	182	75	224	33	233	24	2056
112	139	114	140	146	120	107	150	84	173	184	73	41	216	241	16	2056
101	160	157	148	106	104	98	154	176	81	78	179	51	206	13	244	2056
156	97	100	109	151	153	103	159	174	83	63	194	221	36	7	250	2056
80	169	178	171	96	166	92	87	82	164	183	74	205	52	14	243	2056
177	88	79	86	161	91	165	170	93	175	199	58	207	50	256	1	2056
189	57	188	195	71	76	59	65	70	185	196	191	32	225	248	9	2056
68	200	69	62	186	181	198	192	187	72	66	61	209	48	29	228	2056
47	215	53	35	226	211	43	34	54	201	208	39	220	213	8	249	2056
210	42	204	222	31	46	214	223	203	56	49	218	44	37	23	234	2056
4	254	232	15	239	22	2	246	20	26	245	252	6	28	238	227	2056
253	3	25	242	18	235	255	11	237	231	12	5	251	229	30	19	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

It is a cornered magic square of order 16 where upper-left to below are magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, etc.

For more details refer author's work [35, 36, 37, 38].

2.6 Double-Digit Bordered Magic Squares

Example 2.10.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														2056	
254	255	1	4	5	251	250	8	9	247	246	12	242	243	13	16	2056
3	2	256	253	252	6	7	249	248	10	11	245	15	14	244	241	2056
53	204	60	57	199	198	61	195	194	64	65	68	190	191	17	240	2056
203	54	197	200	58	59	196	62	63	193	192	189	67	66	239	18	2056
202	55	93	164	99	97	159	157	156	154	104	102	69	188	238	19	2056
56	201	163	94	158	160	98	100	101	103	153	155	187	70	20	237	2056
49	208	162	95	113	144	127	132	121	134	117	140	186	71	21	236	2056
207	50	96	161	116	141	122	133	128	131	120	137	72	185	235	22	2056
206	51	89	168	143	114	136	123	130	125	139	118	73	184	234	23	2056
52	205	167	90	142	115	129	126	135	124	138	119	183	74	24	233	2056
45	212	166	91	149	151	105	107	112	110	146	148	182	75	25	232	2056
211	46	92	165	108	106	152	150	145	147	111	109	76	181	231	26	2056
210	47	171	170	88	85	81	175	174	84	178	179	77	80	230	27	2056
48	209	86	87	169	172	176	82	83	173	79	78	180	177	28	229	2056
44	41	214	215	37	219	218	40	33	223	222	36	29	32	227	226	2056
213	216	43	42	220	38	39	217	224	34	35	221	228	225	30	31	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

It is a double-digit bordered magic square of order 16. Removing the higher borders still we are left with magic squares of lower orders, such as of orders 12, 8 and 4. The internal block is a pandiagonal magic square of order 4.

Example 2.11.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														2056	
252	226	244	17	16	214	7	216	204	18	48	36	254	210	45	49	2056
5	31	13	240	241	43	250	41	53	239	209	221	3	47	212	208	2056
10	247	89	85	199	69	66	161	83	173	62	200	184	171	253	4	2056
235	22	168	172	58	188	191	96	174	84	195	57	73	86	222	35	2056
39	218	187	70	101	153	108	157	112	98	160	139	170	87	256	1	2056
33	224	60	197	156	104	149	100	145	159	97	118	61	196	24	233	2056
242	15	88	169	107	150	127	132	121	134	117	140	194	63	201	56	2056
14	243	79	178	142	115	122	133	128	131	105	152	181	76	26	231	2056
11	246	177	80	146	111	136	123	130	125	148	109	91	166	54	203	2056
37	220	183	74	119	138	129	126	135	124	144	113	92	165	20	237	2056
238	19	64	193	120	141	147	114	151	99	154	102	77	180	206	51	2056
236	21	190	67	137	116	110	143	106	158	103	155	162	95	225	32	2056
213	44	163	176	192	78	93	182	71	82	167	198	68	72	28	229	2056
234	23	94	81	65	179	164	75	186	175	90	59	189	185	27	230	2056
215	211	248	25	8	6	30	52	207	34	55	255	29	217	219	245	2056
42	46	9	232	249	251	227	205	50	223	202	2	228	40	38	12	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

*It is a also **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 16 written in little different way. Here we don't have block of order 2×2 as in the previous example. Removing the higher borders still we are left with magic squares of lower orders, such as of orders 12, 8 and 4. The internal block is a pandiagonal magic square of order 4.*

Example 2.12.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														2056	
227	225	29	238	41	9	34	16	240	247	20	37	222	214	3	254	2056
30	32	228	19	216	248	223	241	17	10	237	220	35	43	33	224	2056
205	52	168	75	95	72	173	85	93	165	161	198	77	180	24	233	2056
208	49	89	182	162	185	84	172	164	92	96	59	81	176	217	40	2056
201	56	186	71	100	110	149	153	154	105	107	150	183	74	212	45	2056
38	219	76	181	157	147	108	104	103	152	111	146	194	63	226	31	2056
46	211	60	197	139	118	127	132	121	134	116	141	169	88	1	256	2056
249	8	80	177	115	142	122	133	128	131	137	120	67	190	55	202	2056
231	26	91	166	113	144	136	123	130	125	140	117	170	87	232	25	2056
218	39	58	199	98	159	129	126	135	124	160	97	70	187	54	203	2056
47	210	175	82	155	102	143	156	145	99	119	109	83	174	255	2	2056
221	36	163	94	151	106	114	101	112	158	138	148	191	66	27	230	2056
15	242	200	57	73	69	68	167	192	195	79	193	78	171	215	42	2056
44	213	196	61	184	188	189	90	65	62	178	64	179	86	245	12	2056
53	204	18	11	6	28	236	50	14	206	253	244	22	209	250	252	2056
23	234	239	246	251	229	21	207	243	51	4	13	235	48	7	5	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

It is a alsodouble-digit bordered magic square of order 16 written in little different way. In each blocks the magic rectangles are of equal width and length. We call these types as cyclic magic rectangles. Removing the higher borders still we are left with magic squares of lower orders, such as of orders 12, 8 and 4. The internal block is a pandiagonal magic square of order 4.

For more details refer author's work [33, 34]

2.7 Striped Magic Squares of Order 16

Example 2.13.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				©IJT	2056						
252	226	244	17	16	214	7	216	204	18	48	36	254	210	45	49	2056
5	31	13	240	241	43	250	41	53	239	209	221	3	47	212	208	2056
10	247	89	85	199	69	66	161	83	173	62	200	184	171	253	4	2056
235	22	168	172	58	188	191	96	174	84	195	57	73	86	222	35	2056
39	218	187	70	101	153	108	157	112	98	160	139	170	87	256	1	2056
33	224	60	197	156	104	149	100	145	159	97	118	61	196	24	233	2056
242	15	88	169	107	150	135	122	134	123	117	140	194	63	201	56	2056
14	243	79	178	142	115	128	129	125	132	105	152	181	76	26	231	2056
11	246	177	80	146	111	121	136	124	133	148	109	91	166	54	203	2056
37	220	183	74	119	138	130	127	131	126	144	113	92	165	20	237	2056
238	19	64	193	120	141	147	114	151	99	154	102	77	180	206	51	2056
236	21	190	67	137	116	110	143	106	158	103	155	162	95	225	32	2056
213	44	163	176	192	78	93	182	71	82	167	198	68	72	28	229	2056
234	23	94	81	65	179	164	75	186	175	90	59	189	185	27	230	2056
215	211	248	25	8	6	30	52	207	34	55	255	29	217	219	245	2056
42	46	9	232	249	251	227	205	50	223	202	2	228	40	38	12	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

It is a also **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 16 formed by magic rectangle strips of equal width. The only difference is in the length of each magic rectangle. These types of magic squares we call as striped magic squares.

Example 2.14.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														2056	
227	225	29	238	41	9	34	16	240	247	20	37	222	214	3	254	2056
30	32	228	19	216	248	223	241	17	10	237	220	35	43	33	224	2056
205	52	168	75	95	72	173	85	93	165	161	198	77	180	24	233	2056
208	49	89	182	162	185	84	172	164	92	96	59	81	176	217	40	2056
201	56	186	71	100	110	149	153	154	105	107	150	183	74	212	45	2056
38	219	76	181	157	147	108	104	103	152	111	146	194	63	226	31	2056
46	211	60	197	139	118	135	122	134	123	116	141	169	88	1	256	2056
249	8	80	177	115	142	128	129	125	132	137	120	67	190	55	202	2056
231	26	91	166	113	144	121	136	124	133	140	117	170	87	232	25	2056
218	39	58	199	98	159	130	127	131	126	160	97	70	187	54	203	2056
47	210	175	82	155	102	143	156	145	99	119	109	83	174	255	2	2056
221	36	163	94	151	106	114	101	112	158	138	148	191	66	27	230	2056
15	242	200	57	73	69	68	167	192	195	79	193	78	171	215	42	2056
44	213	196	61	184	188	189	90	65	62	178	64	179	86	245	12	2056
53	204	18	11	6	28	236	50	14	206	253	244	22	209	250	252	2056
23	234	239	246	251	229	21	207	243	51	4	13	235	48	7	5	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

*It is a also **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 16 formed by magic rectangle strips of equal width. The only difference is in the length of each magic rectangle. These types if magic squares we call as striped magic squares.*

Example 2.15.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/								https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				©IJT	2056		
125	131	130	128	117	140	113	144	89	168	81	176	47	210	33	224	2056
132	126	127	129	139	118	143	114	167	90	175	82	209	48	43	214	2056
121	135	134	124	138	119	142	115	91	166	83	174	45	212	35	222	2056
136	122	123	133	120	137	116	141	165	92	173	84	211	46	221	36	2056
105	151	107	149	148	110	146	112	164	93	172	85	208	49	220	37	2056
152	106	150	108	109	147	111	145	94	163	86	171	207	50	219	38	2056
97	159	99	157	156	154	102	104	162	95	170	87	51	206	39	218	2056
160	98	158	100	101	103	155	153	96	161	88	169	52	205	40	217	2056
69	187	71	185	184	183	75	76	77	179	79	177	53	204	41	216	2056
188	70	186	72	73	74	182	181	180	78	178	80	203	54	215	42	2056
57	199	59	197	196	195	63	64	65	191	67	189	55	202	223	34	2056
200	58	198	60	61	62	194	193	192	66	190	68	201	56	213	44	2056
17	239	19	237	236	22	234	24	25	231	27	228	229	30	226	32	2056
240	18	238	20	21	235	23	233	232	26	230	29	28	227	31	225	2056
253	11	3	255	252	6	250	8	9	247	242	245	244	14	1	16	2056
4	246	254	2	5	251	7	249	248	10	15	12	13	243	256	241	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

*It is a also **double-digit corner type** magic square of order 16 formed by magic rectangle strips of equal width. The only difference is in the length of each magic rectangle. These types if magic squares we call as striped magic squares.*

Example 2.16.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				©IJT				2056			
12	246	247	9	8	250	251	5	44	214	215	41	40	218	219	37	2056
245	11	10	248	249	7	6	252	213	43	42	216	217	39	38	220	2056
1	255	254	4	13	243	242	16	33	223	222	36	45	211	210	48	2056
256	2	3	253	244	14	15	241	224	34	35	221	212	46	47	209	2056
25	231	230	28	24	234	235	21	57	199	198	60	56	202	203	53	2056
232	26	27	229	233	23	22	236	200	58	59	197	201	55	54	204	2056
20	238	239	17	29	227	226	32	52	206	207	49	61	195	194	64	2056
237	19	18	240	228	30	31	225	205	51	50	208	196	62	63	193	2056
76	182	183	73	72	186	187	69	108	150	151	105	104	154	155	101	2056
181	75	74	184	185	71	70	188	149	107	106	152	153	103	102	156	2056
65	191	190	68	77	179	178	80	97	159	158	100	109	147	146	112	2056
192	66	67	189	180	78	79	177	160	98	99	157	148	110	111	145	2056
89	167	166	92	88	170	171	85	121	135	134	124	120	138	139	117	2056
168	90	91	165	169	87	86	172	136	122	123	133	137	119	118	140	2056
84	174	175	81	93	163	162	96	116	142	143	113	125	131	130	128	2056
173	83	82	176	164	94	95	161	141	115	114	144	132	126	127	129	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

It is a also striped magic square of order 16 as it is formed by equal width and length of magic rectangles, i.e., 2×4 .

For more details refer author's work [39, 41, 45].

2.8 Different Styles of Magic Squares

Example 2.17.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				©IJT	2056						
75	78	183	178	252	256	3	250	4	6	87	172	88	165	168	91	2056
180	83	174	77	2	17	242	11	244	255	90	94	164	161	95	167	2056
76	176	81	181	8	12	243	18	241	249	171	163	93	96	162	86	2056
184	173	84	73	10	246	13	240	15	247	166	85	169	92	89	170	2056
177	82	175	80	248	239	16	245	14	9	234	232	21	238	22	24	2056
79	179	74	182	251	1	254	7	253	5	28	35	224	29	226	229	2056
198	196	57	202	58	60	127	132	121	134	26	30	225	36	223	231	2056
56	71	188	65	190	201	122	133	128	131	20	228	31	222	33	237	2056
62	66	189	72	187	195	136	123	130	125	230	221	34	227	32	27	2056
64	192	67	186	69	193	129	126	135	124	233	25	236	19	235	23	2056
194	185	70	191	68	63	216	40	39	220	214	42	103	155	98	158	2056
197	61	200	55	199	59	44	53	206	47	208	213	160	107	150	97	2056
115	148	112	144	141	111	38	48	207	54	205	219	100	152	105	157	2056
143	118	140	137	119	114	46	210	49	204	51	211	153	149	108	104	2056
110	139	117	120	138	147	212	203	52	209	50	45	156	106	151	101	2056
146	109	145	113	116	142	215	217	218	37	43	41	99	102	159	154	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

It is a magic square of order 16 formed by magic, bordered magic and bordered magic rectangles.

Example 2.18.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/							https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/							©IJT	2056
183	74	1	255	254	253	2	6	101	155	154	104	105	150	151	108	2056
76	181	250	8	248	9	11	245	156	102	103	153	152	107	106	149	2056
182	75	244	243	15	16	240	13	109	148	19	237	236	235	20	24	2056
73	184	18	14	241	242	17	239	147	110	232	26	230	27	29	227	2056
77	180	7	246	10	247	249	12	146	111	226	225	33	34	222	31	2056
179	78	251	5	3	4	252	256	112	145	36	32	223	224	35	221	2056
178	79	89	167	166	92	85	172	144	113	25	228	28	229	231	30	2056
80	177	168	90	91	165	171	86	114	143	233	23	21	22	234	238	2056
55	201	200	199	56	60	170	87	115	142	117	139	138	120	125	132	2056
196	62	194	63	65	191	88	169	141	116	140	118	119	137	131	126	2056
190	189	69	70	186	67	121	136	37	219	218	217	38	42	130	127	2056
72	68	187	188	71	185	135	122	214	44	212	45	47	209	128	129	2056
61	192	64	193	195	66	134	123	208	207	51	52	204	49	81	176	2056
197	59	57	58	198	202	124	133	54	50	205	206	53	203	174	83	2056
93	162	163	96	97	159	158	100	43	210	46	211	213	48	175	82	2056
164	95	94	161	160	98	99	157	215	41	39	40	216	220	84	173	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

It is a magic square of order 16 formed by magic squares and magic rectangles.

Example 2.19.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/					https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/					©IJT	2056				
249	2	12	14	241	253	109	150	104	151	201	50	60	62	193	205	2056
251	31	24	235	224	6	152	139	118	105	203	79	72	187	176	54	2056
7	223	217	40	34	250	113	122	135	144	55	175	86	171	82	202	2056
5	30	214	43	227	252	108	129	128	149	53	78	172	85	179	204	2056
256	231	39	218	26	1	146	134	123	111	208	188	87	170	69	49	2056
19	236	211	46	21	238	114	119	138	143	66	183	163	94	74	191	2056
244	25	220	37	232	13	98	120	137	159	196	73	166	91	184	61	2056
10	23	44	213	234	247	147	121	136	110	58	71	92	165	186	199	2056
11	228	209	48	29	246	157	140	117	100	59	180	168	89	77	198	2056
242	28	38	219	229	15	145	116	141	112	194	76	169	88	181	63	2056
254	221	42	215	36	3	156	130	127	101	206	177	93	164	80	51	2056
237	225	45	212	32	20	154	132	125	103	189	173	90	167	84	68	2056
9	35	47	210	222	248	99	142	115	158	57	83	95	162	174	200	2056
18	230	216	41	27	239	155	131	126	102	67	182	161	96	75	190	2056
240	33	233	22	226	17	97	124	133	160	192	81	185	70	178	65	2056
4	255	245	243	16	8	106	107	153	148	52	207	197	195	64	56	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

It is a magic square of order 16 formed by magic rectangles.

Example 2.20.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/								https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/								©IJT	2056
7	4	244	256	254	245	241	9	14	11	112	111	148	115	144	141	2056		
252	26	19	239	17	230	236	237	24	5	149	136	138	117	123	108	2056		
8	23	227	35	29	224	31	225	234	249	106	122	131	126	135	151	2056		
247	229	34	219	40	37	218	223	28	10	147	137	125	132	120	110	2056		
2	235	221	38	217	220	39	36	22	255	105	118	128	129	139	152	2056		
15	25	32	222	228	33	226	30	232	242	150	124	130	127	133	107	2056		
251	233	238	18	240	27	21	20	231	6	143	134	119	140	121	114	2056		
246	253	13	1	3	12	16	248	243	250	116	146	109	142	113	145	2056		
92	170	85	166	89	169	47	44	49	216	214	205	201	54	204	51	2056		
173	160	162	93	99	84	207	66	59	199	57	196	190	197	64	50	2056		
82	98	104	153	159	175	48	63	187	75	184	69	71	185	194	209	2056		
171	161	101	156	96	86	211	189	74	178	80	77	179	183	68	46	2056		
81	100	155	102	157	176	42	65	181	79	177	180	78	76	192	215	2056		
174	94	154	103	163	83	55	195	72	182	73	188	186	70	62	202	2056		
167	158	95	164	97	90	212	193	198	58	200	61	67	60	191	45	2056		
88	87	172	91	168	165	206	213	208	41	43	52	56	203	53	210	2056		
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056		

It is a magic square of order 16 formed by magic rectangles.

For mor details refer author's work [6, 7, 8, 10]

2.9 Four-Digits Bordered Squares

Example 2.21.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				©IJT				2056			
7	252	1	254	15	244	9	246	23	236	17	238	31	228	25	230	2056
2	253	8	251	10	245	16	243	18	237	24	235	26	229	32	227	2056
256	3	250	5	248	11	242	13	240	19	234	21	232	27	226	29	2056
249	6	255	4	241	14	247	12	233	22	239	20	225	30	231	28	2056
95	164	89	166	103	156	97	158	111	148	105	150	39	220	33	222	2056
90	165	96	163	98	157	104	155	106	149	112	147	34	221	40	219	2056
168	91	162	93	160	99	154	101	152	107	146	109	224	35	218	37	2056
161	94	167	92	153	102	159	100	145	110	151	108	217	38	223	36	2056
87	172	81	174	127	132	121	134	119	140	113	142	47	212	41	214	2056
82	173	88	171	122	133	128	131	114	141	120	139	42	213	48	211	2056
176	83	170	85	136	123	130	125	144	115	138	117	216	43	210	45	2056
169	86	175	84	129	126	135	124	137	118	143	116	209	46	215	44	2056
79	180	73	182	71	188	65	190	63	196	57	198	55	204	49	206	2056
74	181	80	179	66	189	72	187	58	197	64	195	50	205	56	203	2056
184	75	178	77	192	67	186	69	200	59	194	61	208	51	202	53	2056
177	78	183	76	185	70	191	68	193	62	199	60	201	54	207	52	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

It is a four-digit bordered magic square of order 16. Four digits means border formed by magic squares of order 4. In this case case easily replace the inner part of the magic square forming magic square of order 8.

Example 2.22.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				©IJT	2056						
7	252	1	254	15	244	9	246	23	236	17	238	31	228	25	230	2056
2	253	8	251	10	245	16	243	18	237	24	235	26	229	32	227	2056
256	3	250	5	248	11	242	13	240	19	234	21	232	27	226	29	2056
249	6	255	4	241	14	247	12	233	22	239	20	225	30	231	28	2056
95	164	89	166	115	112	148	141	144	111	135	122	39	220	33	222	2056
90	165	96	163	143	119	137	140	118	114	124	133	34	221	40	219	2056
168	91	162	93	110	138	120	117	139	147	134	123	224	35	218	37	2056
161	94	167	92	146	145	109	116	113	142	121	136	217	38	223	36	2056
87	172	81	174	130	127	99	160	100	156	153	103	47	212	41	214	2056
82	173	88	171	131	126	102	107	152	149	106	155	42	213	48	211	2056
176	83	170	85	125	132	159	150	105	108	151	98	216	43	210	45	2056
169	86	175	84	128	129	154	97	157	101	104	158	209	46	215	44	2056
79	180	73	182	71	188	65	190	63	196	57	198	55	204	49	206	2056
74	181	80	179	66	189	72	187	58	197	64	195	50	205	56	203	2056
184	75	178	77	192	67	186	69	200	59	194	61	208	51	202	53	2056
177	78	183	76	185	70	191	68	193	62	199	60	201	54	207	52	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

It is a four-digit bordered magic square of order 16 embedded with a magic square of order 8 formed magic bordered magic rectangles.

Example 2.23.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				©IJT	2056						
7	252	1	254	15	244	9	246	23	236	17	238	31	228	25	230	2056
2	253	8	251	10	245	16	243	18	237	24	235	26	229	32	227	2056
256	3	250	5	248	11	242	13	240	19	234	21	232	27	226	29	2056
249	6	255	4	241	14	247	12	233	22	239	20	225	30	231	28	2056
95	164	89	166	104	98	158	160	147	109	149	103	39	220	33	222	2056
90	165	96	163	101	142	140	113	146	114	116	156	34	221	40	219	2056
168	91	162	93	102	112	127	132	121	134	145	155	224	35	218	37	2056
161	94	167	92	107	118	122	133	128	131	139	150	217	38	223	36	2056
87	172	81	174	157	120	136	123	130	125	137	100	47	212	41	214	2056
82	173	88	171	152	138	129	126	135	124	119	105	42	213	48	211	2056
176	83	170	85	151	141	117	144	111	143	115	106	216	43	210	45	2056
169	86	175	84	154	159	99	97	110	148	108	153	209	46	215	44	2056
79	180	73	182	71	188	65	190	63	196	57	198	55	204	49	206	2056
74	181	80	179	66	189	72	187	58	197	64	195	50	205	56	203	2056
184	75	178	77	192	67	186	69	200	59	194	61	208	51	202	53	2056
177	78	183	76	185	70	191	68	193	62	199	60	201	54	207	52	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

It is a four-digit bordered magic square of order 16 embedded with a single-digit bordered magic square of order 8.

Example 2.24.

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				©IJT	2056						
3	256	4	249	252	7	15	244	16	237	240	19	27	30	231	226	2056
6	248	245	11	10	251	18	23	233	236	22	239	232	224	33	25	2056
255	9	12	246	247	2	243	234	24	21	235	14	28	34	223	229	2056
250	1	253	8	5	254	238	13	241	20	17	242	225	35	222	32	2056
75	78	183	178	130	128	123	133	132	126	121	135	228	221	36	29	2056
184	83	174	73	159	149	150	103	106	156	105	100	31	227	26	230	2056
76	173	84	181	97	115	109	113	143	145	146	160	39	42	219	214	2056
177	176	81	80	104	141	118	137	140	119	116	153	213	47	210	44	2056
180	82	175	77	99	147	139	120	117	138	110	158	40	209	48	217	2056
79	179	74	182	155	111	148	144	114	112	142	102	220	212	45	37	2056
91	167	86	170	157	108	107	154	151	101	152	98	216	46	211	41	2056
172	95	162	85	127	129	134	124	125	131	136	122	43	215	38	218	2056
88	94	163	169	51	208	52	201	204	55	67	64	196	189	192	63	2056
165	164	93	92	54	59	197	200	58	203	191	70	188	185	71	66	2056
168	161	96	89	207	198	60	57	199	50	62	187	69	72	186	195	2056
87	90	171	166	202	49	205	56	53	206	194	193	61	68	65	190	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

It is a four-digit bordered magic square of order 16 formed by bordered magic rectangles.

For more details refer author's work [32]

3 Different Aspects of Magic Squares

Below are few examples of magic square of order 16 representing different aspects. Initially we shall present the idea of **Latin square distributions**.

3.1 Latin Square Distributions

Let's consider the Latin square distributions of magic square of order 16 given in Example 2.1

Example 3.1. *A pair of Latin square decomposition of above magic square of order 16 is given by*

																136
1	10	15	8	2	9	16	7	3	12	13	6	4	11	14	5	136
15	8	1	10	16	7	2	9	13	6	3	12	14	5	4	11	136
8	15	10	1	7	16	9	2	6	13	12	3	5	14	11	4	136
10	1	8	15	9	2	7	16	12	3	6	13	11	4	5	14	136
3	12	13	6	4	11	14	5	1	10	15	8	2	9	16	7	136
13	6	3	12	14	5	4	11	15	8	1	10	16	7	2	9	136
6	13	12	3	5	14	11	4	8	15	10	1	7	16	9	2	136
12	3	6	13	11	4	5	14	10	1	8	15	9	2	7	16	136
4	11	14	5	3	12	13	6	2	9	16	7	1	10	15	8	136
14	5	4	11	13	6	3	12	16	7	2	9	15	8	1	10	136
5	14	11	4	6	13	12	3	7	16	9	2	8	15	10	1	136
11	4	5	14	12	3	6	13	9	2	7	16	10	1	8	15	136
2	9	16	7	1	10	15	8	4	11	14	5	3	12	13	6	136
16	7	2	9	15	8	1	10	14	5	4	11	13	6	3	12	136
7	16	9	2	8	15	10	1	5	14	11	4	6	13	12	3	136
9	2	7	16	10	1	8	15	11	4	5	14	12	3	6	13	136
136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136

																136
1	10	15	8	7	16	9	2	12	3	6	13	14	5	4	11	136
8	15	10	1	2	9	16	7	13	6	3	12	11	4	5	14	136
10	1	8	15	16	7	2	9	3	12	13	6	5	14	11	4	136
15	8	1	10	9	2	7	16	6	13	12	3	4	11	14	5	136
14	5	4	11	12	3	6	13	7	16	9	2	1	10	15	8	136
11	4	5	14	13	6	3	12	2	9	16	7	8	15	10	1	136
5	14	11	4	3	12	13	6	16	7	2	9	10	1	8	15	136
4	11	14	5	6	13	12	3	9	2	7	16	15	8	1	10	136
7	16	9	2	1	10	15	8	14	5	4	11	12	3	6	13	136
2	9	16	7	8	15	10	1	11	4	5	14	13	6	3	12	136
16	7	2	9	10	1	8	15	5	14	11	4	3	12	13	6	136
9	2	7	16	15	8	1	10	4	11	14	5	6	13	12	3	136
12	3	6	13	14	5	4	11	1	10	15	8	7	16	9	2	136
13	6	3	12	11	4	5	14	8	15	10	1	2	9	16	7	136
3	12	13	6	5	14	11	4	10	1	8	15	16	7	2	9	136
6	13	12	3	4	11	14	5	15	8	1	10	9	2	7	16	136
136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136

In this case, we have a **pair of mutually orthogonal diagonalized Latin squares**. Considering an operation $16 \times (A - 1) + B$, we get magic square of order 16 given in Example 2.1.

Grid 1. Let's write the above Latin squares in terms of a Grid, where numbers are represented by alphabets.

a	j	p	h	b	i	q	g	c	l	m	f	d	k	n	e
p	h	a	j	q	g	b	i	m	f	c	l	n	e	d	k
h	p	j	a	g	q	i	b	f	m	l	c	e	n	k	d
j	a	h	p	i	b	g	q	l	c	f	m	k	d	e	n
c	l	m	f	d	k	n	e	a	j	p	h	b	i	q	g
m	f	c	l	n	e	d	k	p	h	a	j	q	g	b	i
f	m	l	c	e	n	k	d	h	p	j	a	g	q	i	b
l	c	f	m	k	d	e	n	j	a	h	p	i	b	g	q
d	k	n	e	c	l	m	f	b	i	q	g	a	j	p	h
n	e	d	k	m	f	c	l	q	g	b	i	p	h	a	j
e	n	k	d	f	m	l	c	g	q	i	b	h	p	j	a
k	d	e	n	l	c	f	m	i	b	g	q	j	a	h	p
b	i	q	g	a	j	p	h	d	k	n	e	c	l	m	f
q	g	b	i	p	h	a	j	n	e	d	k	m	f	c	l
g	q	i	b	h	p	j	a	e	n	k	d	f	m	l	c
i	b	g	q	j	a	h	p	k	d	e	n	l	c	f	m
								A							

a	j	p	h	g	q	i	b	l	c	f	m	n	e	d	k
h	p	j	a	b	i	q	g	m	f	c	l	k	d	e	n
j	a	h	p	q	g	b	i	c	l	m	f	e	n	k	d
p	h	a	j	i	b	g	q	f	m	l	c	d	k	n	e
n	e	d	k	l	c	f	m	g	q	i	b	a	j	p	h
k	d	e	n	m	f	c	l	b	i	q	g	h	p	j	a
e	n	k	d	c	l	m	f	q	g	b	i	j	a	h	p
d	k	n	e	f	m	l	c	i	b	g	q	p	h	a	j
g	q	i	b	a	j	p	h	n	e	d	k	l	c	f	m
b	i	q	g	h	p	j	a	k	d	e	n	m	f	c	l
q	g	b	i	j	a	h	p	e	n	k	d	c	l	m	f
i	b	g	q	p	h	a	j	d	k	n	e	f	m	l	c
l	c	f	m	n	e	d	k	a	j	p	h	g	q	i	b
m	f	c	l	k	d	e	n	h	p	j	a	b	i	q	g
c	l	m	f	e	n	k	d	j	a	h	p	q	g	b	i
f	m	l	c	d	k	n	e	p	h	a	j	i	b	g	q
								B							

More study of magic squares using the idea of Latin squares refer the author's work [46, 47].

3.2 Palindromic with Equal Sum Blocks of Order 4

Example 3.2. A *pandiagonal magic square of order 16 with equal sum pandiagonal magic squares of order 4* is given by

	pan	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960
479960	26362	34643	13331	45654	24442	36563	15451	43534	28182	32823	11111	47874	22222	38783	17271	41714	479960
479960	13631	45354	26662	34343	15551	43434	24542	36463	11811	47174	28882	32123	17771	41214	22722	38283	479960
479960	46664	14341	33633	25352	44544	16461	35553	23432	48884	12121	31813	27172	42724	18281	37773	21212	479960
479960	33333	25652	46364	14641	35453	23532	44444	16561	31113	27872	48184	12821	37273	21712	42224	18781	479960
479960	28282	32723	11211	47774	22122	38883	17171	41814	26462	34543	13431	45554	24342	36663	15351	43634	479960
479960	11711	47274	28782	32223	17871	41114	22822	38183	13531	45454	26562	34443	15651	43334	24642	36363	479960
479960	48784	12221	31713	27272	42824	18181	37873	21112	46564	14441	33533	25452	44644	16361	35653	23332	479960
479960	31213	27772	48284	12721	37173	21812	42124	18881	33433	25552	46464	14541	35353	23632	44344	16661	479960
479960	22422	38583	17471	41514	28382	32623	11311	47674	24242	36763	15251	43734	26162	34843	13131	45854	479960
479960	17571	41414	22522	38483	11611	47374	28682	32323	15751	43234	24742	36263	13831	45154	26862	34143	479960
479960	42524	18481	37573	21412	48684	12321	31613	27372	44744	16261	35753	23232	46864	14141	33833	25152	479960
479960	37473	21512	42424	18581	31313	27672	48384	12621	35253	23732	44244	16761	33133	25852	46164	14841	479960
479960	24142	36863	15151	43834	26262	34743	13231	45754	22322	38683	17371	41614	28482	32523	11411	47574	479960
479960	15851	43134	24842	36163	13731	45254	26762	34243	17671	41314	22622	38383	11511	47474	28582	32423	479960
479960	44844	16161	35853	23132	46764	14241	33733	25252	42624	18381	37673	21312	48584	12421	31513	27472	479960
	35153	23832	44144	16861	33233	25752	46264	14741	37373	21612	42324	18681	31413	27572	48484	12521	479960
	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{16 \times 16} = 479960$. All the 4×4 blocks are *pandiagonal magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums*, $S_{4 \times 4} = 119990$.

3.3 Palindromic Bimagic Square

Example 3.3. A *bimagic square* of order 16 is given by

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				©IJT	479960							
11111	34243	46764	27872	13731	32823	48184	25252	16461	37373	41614	24542	18681	35553	43434	22322	479960	
45854	28782	12221	33133	47274	26162	14841	31713	42524	23632	15351	38483	44344	21412	17571	36663	479960	
28282	45154	33833	12721	26862	47774	31213	14141	23332	42424	38583	15651	21512	44644	36363	17471	479960	
34743	11811	27172	46264	32123	13231	25752	48884	37673	16561	24442	41314	35453	18381	22622	43534	479960	
16661	37573	41414	24342	18481	35353	43634	22522	11711	34843	46164	27272	13131	32223	48784	25852	479960	
42324	23432	15551	38683	44544	21612	17371	36463	45254	28182	12821	33733	47874	26762	14241	31113	479960	
23532	42624	38383	15451	21312	44444	36563	17671	28882	45754	33233	12121	26262	47174	31813	14741	479960	
37473	16361	24642	41514	35653	18581	22422	43334	34143	11211	27772	46864	32723	13831	25152	48284	479960	
17771	36863	44144	21212	15151	38283	42724	23832	14641	31513	47474	26362	12421	33333	45654	28582	479960	
43234	22122	18881	35753	41814	24742	16261	37173	48384	25452	13531	32623	46564	27672	11311	34443	479960	
22822	43734	35253	18181	24242	41114	37873	16761	25552	48684	32323	13431	27372	46464	34543	11611	479960	
36163	17271	21712	44844	38783	15851	23132	42224	31413	14341	26662	47574	33633	12521	28482	45354	479960	
14441	31313	47674	26562	12621	33533	45454	28382	17171	36263	44744	21812	15751	38883	42124	23232	479960	
48584	25652	13331	32423	46364	27472	11511	34643	43834	22722	18281	35153	41214	24142	16861	37773	479960	
25352	48484	32523	13631	27572	46664	34343	11411	22222	43134	35853	18781	24842	41714	37273	16161	479960	
31613	14541	26462	47374	33433	12321	28682	45554	36763	17871	21112	44244	38183	15251	23732	42824	479960	
479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960	479960

In this case, the magic and *bimagic* sums are $S_{16 \times 16} := 479960$ and $Sb_{16 \times 16} := 16484528520$ respectively. Details of this *bimagic* square can be seen in author's work [?]. The blocks of order 4 are also magic squares with equal magic sums $S_{4 \times 4} := 119990$

For more details refer author's work [12, 13]

3.4 Perfect Square Entries Sum

Below are five different magic squares of order 16 resulting in **uniformity**, **Pythagorean triples** and **minimum perfect square sum** properties. Out of these five, three of them are with **fraction numbers** entries.

3.4.1 Uniformity Property

Example 3.4. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 16 for consecutive odd numbers entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 509, 511\}$ is given by

	pan	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096
4096	13	503	1	507	29	487	17	491	45	471	33	475	61	455	49	459	4096
4096	3	505	15	501	19	489	31	485	35	473	47	469	51	457	63	453	4096
4096	511	5	499	9	495	21	483	25	479	37	467	41	463	53	451	57	4096
4096	497	11	509	7	481	27	493	23	465	43	477	39	449	59	461	55	4096
4096	77	439	65	443	93	423	81	427	109	407	97	411	125	391	113	395	4096
4096	67	441	79	437	83	425	95	421	99	409	111	405	115	393	127	389	4096
4096	447	69	435	73	431	85	419	89	415	101	403	105	399	117	387	121	4096
4096	433	75	445	71	417	91	429	87	401	107	413	103	385	123	397	119	4096
4096	141	375	129	379	157	359	145	363	173	343	161	347	189	327	177	331	4096
4096	131	377	143	373	147	361	159	357	163	345	175	341	179	329	191	325	4096
4096	383	133	371	137	367	149	355	153	351	165	339	169	335	181	323	185	4096
4096	369	139	381	135	353	155	365	151	337	171	349	167	321	187	333	183	4096
4096	205	311	193	315	221	295	209	299	237	279	225	283	253	263	241	267	4096
4096	195	313	207	309	211	297	223	293	227	281	239	277	243	265	255	261	4096
4096	319	197	307	201	303	213	291	217	287	229	275	233	271	245	259	249	4096
	305	203	317	199	289	219	301	215	273	235	285	231	257	251	269	247	4096
	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096

Example 3.5. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 16 for consecutive fraction numbers entries $\{257/2, 259/2, \dots, 763/2, 767/2\}$ is given by

	pan	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096
4096	134.5	379.5	128.5	381.5	142.5	371.5	136.5	373.5	150.5	363.5	144.5	365.5	158.5	355.5	152.5	357.5	4096
4096	129.5	380.5	135.5	378.5	137.5	372.5	143.5	370.5	145.5	364.5	151.5	362.5	153.5	356.5	159.5	354.5	4096
4096	383.5	130.5	377.5	132.5	375.5	138.5	369.5	140.5	367.5	146.5	361.5	148.5	359.5	154.5	353.5	156.5	4096
4096	376.5	133.5	382.5	131.5	368.5	141.5	374.5	139.5	360.5	149.5	366.5	147.5	352.5	157.5	358.5	155.5	4096
4096	166.5	347.5	160.5	349.5	174.5	339.5	168.5	341.5	182.5	331.5	176.5	333.5	190.5	323.5	184.5	325.5	4096
4096	161.5	348.5	167.5	346.5	169.5	340.5	175.5	338.5	177.5	332.5	183.5	330.5	185.5	324.5	191.5	322.5	4096
4096	351.5	162.5	345.5	164.5	343.5	170.5	337.5	172.5	335.5	178.5	329.5	180.5	327.5	186.5	321.5	188.5	4096
4096	344.5	165.5	350.5	163.5	336.5	173.5	342.5	171.5	328.5	181.5	334.5	179.5	320.5	189.5	326.5	187.5	4096
4096	198.5	315.5	192.5	317.5	206.5	307.5	200.5	309.5	214.5	299.5	208.5	301.5	222.5	291.5	216.5	293.5	4096
4096	193.5	316.5	199.5	314.5	201.5	308.5	207.5	306.5	209.5	300.5	215.5	298.5	217.5	292.5	223.5	290.5	4096
4096	319.5	194.5	313.5	196.5	311.5	202.5	305.5	204.5	303.5	210.5	297.5	212.5	295.5	218.5	289.5	220.5	4096
4096	312.5	197.5	318.5	195.5	304.5	205.5	310.5	203.5	296.5	213.5	302.5	211.5	288.5	221.5	294.5	219.5	4096
4096	230.5	283.5	224.5	285.5	238.5	275.5	232.5	277.5	246.5	267.5	240.5	269.5	254.5	259.5	248.5	261.5	4096
4096	225.5	284.5	231.5	282.5	233.5	276.5	239.5	274.5	241.5	268.5	247.5	266.5	249.5	260.5	255.5	258.5	4096
4096	287.5	226.5	281.5	228.5	279.5	234.5	273.5	236.5	271.5	242.5	265.5	244.5	263.5	250.5	257.5	252.5	4096
	280.5	229.5	286.5	227.5	272.5	237.5	278.5	235.5	264.5	245.5	270.5	243.5	256.5	253.5	262.5	251.5	4096
	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096

Both the Examples 3.4 and 3.5 are with equal magic sums. The blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums. See the details below:

$$S_{16 \times 16} = 4096 = 16^3; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 4096 = 65536 = 256^2 = 16^4$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 1024; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 1024 = 4096 = 64^2.$$

The Examples 3.4 and 3.5 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 16, 16^2, 16^3, 16^4 \rangle$.

3.4.2 Pythagorean Triple

Example 3.6. A *block-wise pandiagonal* square of order 16 for consecutive odd numbers entries $\{69, 71, \dots, 577, 579\}$ is given by

	pan	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096
4096	13	503	1	507	29	487	17	491	45	471	33	475	61	455	49	459	4096
4096	3	505	15	501	19	489	31	485	35	473	47	469	51	457	63	453	4096
4096	511	5	499	9	495	21	483	25	479	37	467	41	463	53	451	57	4096
4096	497	11	509	7	481	27	493	23	465	43	477	39	449	59	461	55	4096
4096	77	439	65	443	93	423	81	427	109	407	97	411	125	391	113	395	4096
4096	67	441	79	437	83	425	95	421	99	409	111	405	115	393	127	389	4096
4096	447	69	435	73	431	85	419	89	415	101	403	105	399	117	387	121	4096
4096	433	75	445	71	417	91	429	87	401	107	413	103	385	123	397	119	4096
4096	141	375	129	379	157	359	145	363	173	343	161	347	189	327	177	331	4096
4096	131	377	143	373	147	361	159	357	163	345	175	341	179	329	191	325	4096
4096	383	133	371	137	367	149	355	153	351	165	339	169	335	181	323	185	4096
4096	369	139	381	135	353	155	365	151	337	171	349	167	321	187	333	183	4096
4096	205	311	193	315	221	295	209	299	237	279	225	283	253	263	241	267	4096
4096	195	313	207	309	211	297	223	293	227	281	239	277	243	265	255	261	4096
4096	319	197	307	201	303	213	291	217	287	229	275	233	271	245	259	249	4096
	305	203	317	199	289	219	301	215	273	235	285	231	257	251	269	247	4096
	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096

Example 3.7. A *block-wise pandiagonal* square of order 16 for consecutive fraction numbers entries $\{393/2, 395/2, \dots, 901/2, 903/2\}$ is given by

	pan	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	
5184	202.5	447.5	196.5	449.5	210.5	439.5	204.5	441.5	218.5	431.5	212.5	433.5	226.5	423.5	220.5	425.5	5184
5184	197.5	448.5	203.5	446.5	205.5	440.5	211.5	438.5	213.5	432.5	219.5	430.5	221.5	424.5	227.5	422.5	5184
5184	451.5	198.5	445.5	200.5	443.5	206.5	437.5	208.5	435.5	214.5	429.5	216.5	427.5	222.5	421.5	224.5	5184
5184	444.5	201.5	450.5	199.5	436.5	209.5	442.5	207.5	428.5	217.5	434.5	215.5	420.5	225.5	426.5	223.5	5184
5184	234.5	415.5	228.5	417.5	242.5	407.5	236.5	409.5	250.5	399.5	244.5	401.5	258.5	391.5	252.5	393.5	5184
5184	229.5	416.5	235.5	414.5	237.5	408.5	243.5	406.5	245.5	400.5	251.5	398.5	253.5	392.5	259.5	390.5	5184
5184	419.5	230.5	413.5	232.5	411.5	238.5	405.5	240.5	403.5	246.5	397.5	248.5	395.5	254.5	389.5	256.5	5184
5184	412.5	233.5	418.5	231.5	404.5	241.5	410.5	239.5	396.5	249.5	402.5	247.5	388.5	257.5	394.5	255.5	5184
5184	266.5	383.5	260.5	385.5	274.5	375.5	268.5	377.5	282.5	367.5	276.5	369.5	290.5	359.5	284.5	361.5	5184
5184	261.5	384.5	267.5	382.5	269.5	376.5	275.5	374.5	277.5	368.5	283.5	366.5	285.5	360.5	291.5	358.5	5184
5184	387.5	262.5	381.5	264.5	379.5	270.5	373.5	272.5	371.5	278.5	365.5	280.5	363.5	286.5	357.5	288.5	5184
5184	380.5	265.5	386.5	263.5	372.5	273.5	378.5	271.5	364.5	281.5	370.5	279.5	356.5	289.5	362.5	287.5	5184
5184	298.5	351.5	292.5	353.5	306.5	343.5	300.5	345.5	314.5	335.5	308.5	337.5	322.5	327.5	316.5	329.5	5184
5184	293.5	352.5	299.5	350.5	301.5	344.5	307.5	342.5	309.5	336.5	315.5	334.5	317.5	328.5	323.5	326.5	5184
5184	355.5	294.5	349.5	296.5	347.5	302.5	341.5	304.5	339.5	310.5	333.5	312.5	331.5	318.5	325.5	320.5	5184
	348.5	297.5	354.5	295.5	340.5	305.5	346.5	303.5	332.5	313.5	338.5	311.5	324.5	321.5	330.5	319.5	5184
	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184

Both the Examples 3.6 and 3.7 are with equal magic sums. The blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums. See the details below:

$$S_{16 \times 16} = 5184; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 5184 = 82944 = 288^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} = 1296; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 1296 = 5184 = 72^2.$$

Both the Examples 3.6 and 3.7 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (34, 288, 290)**, i.e., $34^2 + 288^2 = 290^2$ with least possible entries resulting in **perfect square entries sum**.

3.4.3 Minimum Perfect Square Entries Sum

Example 3.8. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 16 for consecutive fraction numbers entries $\{33/2, 35/2, \dots, 541/2, 543/2\}$ is given by

	pan	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304
2304	22.5	267.5	16.5	269.5	30.5	259.5	24.5	261.5	38.5	251.5	32.5	253.5	46.5	243.5	40.5	245.5	2304
2304	17.5	268.5	23.5	266.5	25.5	260.5	31.5	258.5	33.5	252.5	39.5	250.5	41.5	244.5	47.5	242.5	2304
2304	271.5	18.5	265.5	20.5	263.5	26.5	257.5	28.5	255.5	34.5	249.5	36.5	247.5	42.5	241.5	44.5	2304
2304	264.5	21.5	270.5	19.5	256.5	29.5	262.5	27.5	248.5	37.5	254.5	35.5	240.5	45.5	246.5	43.5	2304
2304	54.5	235.5	48.5	237.5	62.5	227.5	56.5	229.5	70.5	219.5	64.5	221.5	78.5	211.5	72.5	213.5	2304
2304	49.5	236.5	55.5	234.5	57.5	228.5	63.5	226.5	65.5	220.5	71.5	218.5	73.5	212.5	79.5	210.5	2304
2304	239.5	50.5	233.5	52.5	231.5	58.5	225.5	60.5	223.5	66.5	217.5	68.5	215.5	74.5	209.5	76.5	2304
2304	232.5	53.5	238.5	51.5	224.5	61.5	230.5	59.5	216.5	69.5	222.5	67.5	208.5	77.5	214.5	75.5	2304
2304	86.5	203.5	80.5	205.5	94.5	195.5	88.5	197.5	102.5	187.5	96.5	189.5	110.5	179.5	104.5	181.5	2304
2304	81.5	204.5	87.5	202.5	89.5	196.5	95.5	194.5	97.5	188.5	103.5	186.5	105.5	180.5	111.5	178.5	2304
2304	207.5	82.5	201.5	84.5	199.5	90.5	193.5	92.5	191.5	98.5	185.5	100.5	183.5	106.5	177.5	108.5	2304
2304	200.5	85.5	206.5	83.5	192.5	93.5	198.5	91.5	184.5	101.5	190.5	99.5	176.5	109.5	182.5	107.5	2304
2304	118.5	171.5	112.5	173.5	126.5	163.5	120.5	165.5	134.5	155.5	128.5	157.5	142.5	147.5	136.5	149.5	2304
2304	113.5	172.5	119.5	170.5	121.5	164.5	127.5	162.5	129.5	156.5	135.5	154.5	137.5	148.5	143.5	146.5	2304
2304	175.5	114.5	169.5	116.5	167.5	122.5	161.5	124.5	159.5	130.5	153.5	132.5	151.5	138.5	145.5	140.5	2304
	168.5	117.5	174.5	115.5	160.5	125.5	166.5	123.5	152.5	133.5	158.5	131.5	144.5	141.5	150.5	139.5	2304
	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**. The blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{16 \times 16} = 2304; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 2304 = 36864 = 192^2$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} = 576; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 576 = 2304 = 48^2.$$

For more details refer author's work [14, 15, 16, 17, 18].

4 Upside-Down, Mirror-Looking and Water Reflection

Let's consider the following image:

Source: <https://www.mathsisfun.com/definitions/vertical-flip.html>

From the above image we understand that **horizontal flip** is same as **mirror looking image** and the **vertical flip** is same as **water reflection image**. The same terms are given in **paint brush of microsoft**. Let's see how it works on numbers.

Let's consider following 9 digits written in digital form:

0-1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9

• 180° Rotation

6-8-1-9-5-4-2-1-0

In this case, the readable numbers are 0, 1, 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9 where the number 6 becomes 9 and 9 as 6. Thus the **survival numbers** after 180° rotation are 0, 1, 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9. Sometimes we call them as **upside-down numbers**.

• Mirror Looking

It is same as **horizontal flip** as describe above. In this case, we have

2-8-7-3-2-4-6-5-1-0

In this case, the readable numbers are 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8, where 2 becomes 5 and 5 as 2. Thus the **survival numbers** after **horizontal flip** are 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8. Sometimes we call them as **mirror-looking** numbers.

• Water Reflection

It is same as **vertical flip** as describe above. In this case, we have

0-1-5-3-4-2-2-1-8-2

In this case, the readable numbers are 0, 1, 2, 3, 5 and 8, where 2 becomes 5 and 5 as 2. Thus the **survival numbers** after **vertical flip** are 0, 1, 2, 3, 5 and 8. For the first time we call these numbers as **water reflection** or **water reflexive** numbers.

We observe that the numbers 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8 are in all the three situations, i.e., these are **upside-down**, **mirror-looking** and **water reflexive**. We call them as **universal numbers** provided they are written in **digital form**. There left only one number 3. It is only **water reflexive**. While the numbers 6 and 9 are only **upside-down**.

There is a lot of work by author on **upside-down** and **mirror-looking** numbers. This work is concentrated only towards magic squares having **water reflexive** numbers, i.e., 0, 1, 2, 3, 5 and 8. The numbers 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8 are already studied previously. This work brings magic squares of order 14 to 16 specially in number 3 along with 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8.

4.1 Upside-Down and Mirror Looking

This section brings magic and **bimagic** squares of order 16 written in such way that, if we make 180° rotation and/or see in the mirror, still we are able to read the entries again resulting in magic squares. It is possible only with the digits 0, 1, 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9 written in digital forms.

Example 4.1. *The magic squares of order 16 for the digits (1,2,5,8) is given by*

2555	5282	1215	8522	2258	5581	1518	8221	2851	5188	1111	8828	2152	5885	1812	8125
1222	8515	2582	5255	1521	8218	2281	5558	1128	8811	2888	5151	1825	8112	2185	5852
8582	1255	5222	2515	8281	1558	5521	2218	8888	1151	5128	2811	8185	1852	5825	2112
5215	2522	8555	1282	5518	2221	8258	1581	5111	2828	8851	1188	5812	2125	8152	1885
2852	5185	1112	8825	2151	5888	1811	8128	2558	5281	1218	8521	2255	5582	1515	8222
1125	8812	2885	5152	1828	8111	2188	5851	1221	8518	2581	5258	1522	8215	2282	5555
8885	1152	5125	2812	8188	1851	5828	2111	8581	1258	5221	2518	8282	1555	5522	2215
5112	2825	8852	1185	5811	2128	8151	1888	5218	2521	8558	1281	5515	2222	8255	1582
2158	5881	1818	8121	2855	5182	1115	8822	2252	5585	1512	8225	2551	5288	1211	8528
1821	8118	2181	5858	1122	8815	2882	5155	1525	8212	2285	5552	1228	8511	2588	5251
8181	1858	5821	2118	8882	1155	5122	2815	8285	1552	5525	2212	8588	1251	5228	2511
5818	2121	8158	1881	5115	2822	8855	1182	5512	2225	8252	1585	5211	2528	8551	1288
2251	5588	1511	8228	2552	5285	1212	8525	2155	5882	1815	8122	2858	5181	1118	8821
1528	8211	2288	5551	1225	8512	2585	5252	1822	8115	2182	5855	1121	8818	2881	5158
8288	1551	5528	2211	8585	1252	5225	2512	8182	1855	5822	2115	8881	1158	5121	2818
5511	2228	8251	1588	5212	2525	8552	1285	5815	2122	8155	1882	5118	2821	8858	1181

The above magic square for the digits (1, 2, 5, 8) is *upside-down* and *mirror-looking*, i.e., it is a *universal* magic squares of order 16 with *magic sum* $S_{16 \times 16}(1, 2, 5, 8) := 71104$. The blocks of order 4 are magic squares with different magic sums.

Example 4.2. *The magic squares of order 16 for the digits (1,6,8,9) is given by*

6999	9686	1619	8966	6698	9981	1918	8661	6891	9188	1111	8868	6196	9889	1816	8169
1666	8919	6986	9699	1961	8618	6681	9998	1168	8811	6888	9191	1869	8116	6189	9896
8986	1699	9666	6919	8681	1998	9961	6618	8888	1191	9168	6811	8189	1896	9869	6116
9619	6966	8999	1686	9918	6661	8698	1981	9111	6868	8891	1188	9816	6169	8196	1889
6896	9189	1116	8869	6191	9888	1811	8168	6998	9681	1618	8961	6699	9986	1919	8666
1169	8816	6889	9196	1868	8111	6188	9891	1661	8918	6981	9698	1966	8619	6686	9999
8889	1196	9169	6816	8188	1891	9868	6111	8981	1698	9661	6918	8686	1999	9966	6619
9116	6869	8896	1189	9811	6168	8191	1888	9618	6961	8998	1681	9919	6666	8699	1986
6198	9881	1818	8161	6899	9186	1119	8866	6696	9989	1916	8669	6991	9688	1611	8968
1861	8118	6181	9898	1166	8819	6886	9199	1969	8616	6689	9996	1668	8911	6988	9691
8181	1898	9861	6118	8886	1199	9166	6819	8689	1996	9969	6616	8988	1691	9668	6911
9818	6161	8198	1881	9119	6866	8899	1186	9916	6669	8696	1989	9611	6968	8991	1688
6691	9988	1911	8668	6996	9689	1616	8969	6199	9886	1819	8166	6898	9181	1118	8861
1968	8611	6688	9991	1669	8916	6989	9696	1866	8119	6186	9899	1161	8818	6881	9198
8688	1991	9968	6611	8989	1696	9669	6916	8186	1899	9866	6119	8881	1198	9161	6818
9911	6668	8691	1988	9616	6969	8996	1689	9819	6166	8199	1886	9118	6861	8898	1181

The above magic square for the digits (1,6,8,9) is only upside-down. In this case the magic sum is $S_{16 \times 16}(1,6,8,9) := 106656$. The blocks of order 4 are magic squares with different magic sums.

Example 4.3. The *bimagic* square of order 16 for the digits (1, 2, 5, 8) is given by

1111	5252	8585	2828	1225	5188	8851	2512	1558	5815	8122	2281	1882	5521	8218	2155
8528	2885	1152	5211	8812	2551	1288	5125	8181	2222	1515	5858	8255	2118	1821	5582
2852	8511	5228	1185	2588	8825	5112	1251	2215	8158	5881	1522	2121	8282	5555	1818
5285	1128	2811	8552	5151	1212	2525	8888	5822	1581	2258	8115	5518	1855	2182	8221
1582	5821	8118	2255	1858	5515	8222	2181	1125	5288	8551	2812	1211	5152	8885	2528
8155	2218	1521	5882	8281	2122	1815	5558	8512	2851	1188	5225	8828	2585	1252	5111
2221	8182	5855	1518	2115	8258	5581	1822	2888	8525	5212	1151	2552	8811	5128	1285
5818	1555	2282	8121	5522	1881	2158	8215	5251	1112	2825	8588	5185	1228	2511	8852
1825	5588	8251	2112	1511	5852	8185	2228	1282	5121	8818	2555	1158	5215	8522	2881
8212	2151	1888	5525	8128	2285	1552	5811	8855	2518	1221	5182	8581	2822	1115	5258
2188	8225	5512	1851	2252	8111	5828	1585	2521	8882	5155	1218	2815	8558	5281	1122
5551	1812	2125	8288	5885	1528	2211	8152	5118	1255	2582	8821	5222	1181	2858	8515
1258	5115	8822	2581	1182	5221	8518	2855	1811	5552	8285	2128	1525	5888	8151	2212
8881	2522	1215	5158	8555	2818	1121	5282	8228	2185	1852	5511	8112	2251	1588	5825
2515	8858	5181	1222	2821	8582	5255	1118	2152	8211	5528	1885	2288	8125	5812	1551
5122	1281	2558	8815	5218	1155	2882	8521	5585	1828	2111	8252	5851	1512	2225	8188

The above magic square for the digits (1, 2, 5, 8) is *upside-down* and *mirror-looking*, i.e., it is a *universal* magic squares of order 16 with *magic sum* $S_{16 \times 16}(1, 2, 5, 8) := 71104$. The blocks of order 4 are magic squares with different magic sums. The *bimagic sums* is $Sb_{16 \times 16}(1, 2, 5, 8) := 437198296$.

Example 4.4. The *bimagic square* of order 16 for the digits (1, 6, 8, 9) is given by

1111	9696	8989	6868	1669	9188	8891	6916	1998	9819	8166	6681	1886	9961	8618	6199
8968	6889	1196	9611	8816	6991	1688	9169	8181	6666	1919	9898	8699	6118	1861	9986
6896	8911	9668	1189	6988	8869	9116	1691	6619	8198	9881	1966	6161	8686	9999	1818
9689	1168	6811	8996	9191	1616	6969	8888	9866	1981	6698	8119	9918	1899	6186	8661
1986	9861	8118	6699	1898	9919	8666	6181	1169	9688	8991	6816	1611	9196	8889	6968
8199	6618	1961	9886	8681	6166	1819	9998	8916	6891	1188	9669	8868	6989	1696	9111
6661	8186	9899	1918	6119	8698	9981	1866	6888	8969	9616	1191	6996	8811	9168	1689
9818	1999	6686	8161	9966	1881	6198	8619	9691	1116	6869	8988	9189	1668	6911	8896
1869	9988	8691	6116	1911	9896	8189	6668	1686	9161	8818	6999	1198	9619	8966	6881
8616	6191	1888	9969	8168	6689	1996	9811	8899	6918	1661	9186	8981	6866	1119	9698
6188	8669	9916	1891	6696	8111	9868	1989	6961	8886	9199	1618	6819	8998	9681	1166
9991	1816	6169	8688	9889	1968	6611	8196	9118	1699	6986	8861	9666	1181	6898	8919
1698	9119	8866	6981	1186	9661	8918	6899	1811	9996	8689	6168	1969	9888	8191	6616
8881	6966	1619	9198	8999	6818	1161	9686	8668	6189	1896	9911	8116	6691	1988	9869
6919	8898	9181	1666	6861	8986	9699	1118	6196	8611	9968	1889	6688	8169	9816	1991
9166	1681	6998	8819	9618	1199	6886	8961	9989	1868	6111	8696	9891	1916	6669	8188

The above magic square with digits (1, 6, 8, 9) is only *upside-down*. In this case the *magic sum* is $S_{16 \times 16}(1, 6, 8, 9) := 106656$. The blocks of order 4 are magic squares with different magic sums. The *bimagic sums* is $Sb_{16 \times 16}(1, 2, 5, 8) := 1170668484$.

Example 4.5. The *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 16 for the digits (1,8), (2,5) and (6,9) are given by

8181818 1881118 88818818 11188181	8181811 18181188 88188811 11818188	81111888 18881111 88888888 11118111	81881881 18111118 88118881 11888118
88818181 11188818 81181181 18811818	88188188 11818811 81811188 18181811	88888111 11118888 81111111 18881888	88118118 11888881 81881118 18111881
11181181 88811818 18818181 81188818	11811188 88181811 18188188 81818811	11111111 88881888 18888111 81118888	11881118 88111881 18118118 81888881
18818818 81188181 11181818 88811181	18188811 81818188 11811811 88181188	18888888 81118111 11111888 88881111	18118881 81888118 11881881 88111118
81111881 18881118 88888881 11118118	81881888 18111111 88118888 11888111	81181811 18811188 88818811 11188188	8181818 18181181 88188818 11818181
88888118 11118881 81111118 18881881	88118111 11888888 81881111 18111888	88818188 11188811 81181188 18811811	88188181 11818818 81811181 18181818
11111118 88881881 18888118 81118881	11881111 88111888 18118111 81888888	11181188 88811811 18818188 81188811	11811181 88181818 18188181 81818818
18888881 81118118 11111881 88881118	18118888 81888111 11881888 88111111	18818811 81188188 11181811 88811188	18188818 81818181 11811818 88181181
81881811 18111188 88118811 11888188	81111818 18881181 88888818 11118181	8181881 18181118 88188881 11818118	81181888 18811111 88818888 11188111
88118188 11888811 81881188 18111811	88888181 11118818 81111181 18881818	88188118 11818881 81811118 18181881	88818111 11188888 81181111 18811888
11881188 88111811 18118188 81888811	11111181 88881818 18888181 81118818	11811118 88181881 18188118 81818881	11181111 88811888 18818111 81188888
18118811 81888188 11881811 88111188	18888818 81118181 11111818 88881181	18188881 81818118 11811881 88181118	18818888 81188111 11181888 88811111
81811888 18181111 88188888 11818111	81181881 18811118 88818881 11188118	81881818 18111181 88118818 11888181	81111811 18881188 88888811 11118188
88188111 11818888 81811111 18181888	88818118 11188881 81181118 18811881	88118181 11888818 81881181 18111818	88888188 11118811 81111188 18881811
11811111 88181888 18188111 81818888	11181118 88811881 18818118 81188881	11881181 88111818 18118181 81888818	11111188 88881811 18888188 81118811
18188888 81818111 11811888 88181111	18818881 81188118 11181881 88811118	18118818 81888181 11881818 88111181	18888811 81118188 11111811 88881188

The magic sums of above magic squares is $S_{16 \times 16}(1,8) := 799999992$. The blocks of order 4 are *pandiagonal* magic squares with equal magic sums. It is *upside-down* and *mirror-looking*, i.e., it is a universal magic square of order 16 for two digits (1,8). It is a *pandiagonal* magic square.

Example 4.6. The *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 16 for the digits (2,5) is given by

52252525	25522252	55525525	22255252	52522522	25252255	55255522	22525255	52222555	25552222	55555555	22225222	52552552	25222225	55225552	22555225
55525252	22255525	52252252	25522525	55255255	22525522	52522255	25252522	55555222	22225555	52222222	25552555	55225225	22555552	52552225	25222552
22252252	55522525	25525252	52255525	22522255	55252522	25255255	52525522	22222222	55552555	25555222	52225555	22552225	55222552	25225225	52555552
25525525	52255252	22225252	55522252	25255522	52525255	22522522	55252255	25555555	52225222	22222555	55552222	25225552	52555225	22522552	55222225
52222552	25552225	55555552	22225225	52552555	25222222	55225555	22555222	52252522	25522255	55525255	22255225	52522525	25252252	55255525	22525252
55555225	22225552	52222225	25552552	55225222	22555555	52552222	25222555	55525255	22255522	52252255	25522522	55255252	22522525	52522525	25252525
22222225	55552552	25555225	52225552	22552222	55222555	25225222	52555555	22252255	55522522	25525255	52255522	22522252	55252525	25255252	52525525
25555552	52225225	22222552	55552225	25225555	52555222	22525555	55222222	25525252	52255255	22252522	55522255	25255525	52525252	22522525	55252252
52552522	25222255	55225522	22555255	52222525	25552252	55555525	22225252	52522552	25252225	55255552	22525225	52252555	25522222	55525555	22255222
55225255	22555522	52552255	25222522	55555252	22225525	52222252	25552525	55255225	22525552	52522225	25252552	55525222	22255555	52252222	25522555
22552255	55222522	25225255	52555522	22222252	55552525	25555252	52225255	22522225	55252552	25255225	52525552	22252222	55522555	25525555	52255555
25225522	52555255	22525222	55222255	25555525	52225252	22222525	55552252	25255552	52525225	22522552	55252225	25525555	52255222	22225555	55522222
52522555	25252222	55255555	22525222	52252552	25522225	55525552	22255225	52552525	25222252	55225525	22555252	52222525	25555222	55555222	22225255
55255222	22525555	52522222	25252555	55525225	22255552	52252225	25522552	55225252	22555525	52552252	25222525	55555255	22225522	52222255	25552522
22522222	55252555	25255222	52525555	22252225	55522552	25525225	52255552	22552252	55222525	25225252	52555525	22222255	55552522	25555255	52225522
25255555	52525222	22522555	55252222	25525552	52255225	22252552	55522225	25225525	52555252	22552525	55222252	25555522	52225255	22222522	55552255

The magic sums of above magic square is $S_{16 \times 16}(2,5) := 622222216$. The blocks of order 4 are *pandiagonal* magic squares with equal magic sums. It is *upside-down* and *mirror-looking*, i.e., it is a universal magic square of order 16 for two digits (2,5). It is a *pandiagonal* magic square.

Example 4.7. The *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 16 for the digits (1,8), (2,5) and (6,9) are given by

9696969	69966696	99969969	66699696	96966966	69696699	99699966	66969699	96666999	69996666	99999999	66669666	96996996	69666669	99669996	66999669
99969696	66699969	96696696	69966969	99699699	66969966	96966699	69696966	99999666	66669999	96666666	69996999	99669669	66999996	96996669	69666996
66696696	99966969	69969696	96699969	66966699	99696966	69699699	96969966	66666666	99996999	69999666	96669999	66996669	99666996	69669669	96999996
69969969	96699696	66696969	99966696	69699666	96969699	66966966	99696699	69999999	96669666	66666999	99996666	69669996	96999669	66996996	99666669
96666996	69996669	99999996	66669669	96996999	69666666	99669999	66999666	96696966	69966699	99969966	66699699	96966969	69696696	99699969	66969696
99999669	66669996	96666669	69996996	99669666	66999999	96996666	69666999	99969699	66699966	96696699	69966966	99699696	66969696	96966696	69696969
66666669	99996996	69999669	96669996	66996666	99666999	69669666	96999999	66696699	99966966	69969699	96699966	66966696	99699696	69699696	96969969
69999996	96669669	66666996	99996669	69669999	96999666	66996999	99666666	69969966	96699699	66696966	99966699	69699969	96969696	66966696	99696696
96996966	69666699	99669966	66999699	96669696	69996696	99999696	66669696	96966996	69696669	99699996	66969669	96696999	69966666	99969999	66699666
99669699	66999666	96996699	69666966	99999696	66669969	96666696	69996969	99699669	66969996	96966669	69696996	99969666	66699999	96696666	69966999
66996699	99666966	69669699	96999666	66666696	99996969	69999696	96669969	66966669	99696996	69699669	96969996	66696666	99966999	69969666	96699999
69669966	96999699	66996966	99666699	69999696	96669696	66666969	99996696	69699996	96969669	66966996	99696669	69969999	96699666	66696999	99966666
96966999	69696666	99699999	66969666	96696996	69966669	99969996	66699669	96996969	69666696	99669969	66999696	96666966	69996699	99999666	66669699
99699666	66969999	96966666	69696999	99969669	66699996	96696669	69966996	99669696	66999696	96966696	69666969	99999699	66669966	96666699	69996966
66966666	99696999	69699666	96969999	66696669	99966996	69969669	96699996	66996696	99666969	69669696	96999699	66666699	99996966	69999699	96669966
69699999	96969666	66966999	99696666	69969996	96699669	66696996	99966669	69669969	96999696	66969696	99666969	69999666	96669699	66666966	99996699

The magic sums of above magic square is $S_{16 \times 16}(6,9) := 1333333320$. The blocks of order 4 are *pandiagonal* magic squares with equal magic sums. It is only *upside-down* in two digits (6,9). It is a *pandiagonal* magic square.

Below are three examples of **bimagic** squares of order 16 for the digits (1,8), (2,5) and (6,9).

Example 4.8. The *bimagic* squares of order 16 for the digits (1,8) is given by

88888888	1881881	1118118	8118111	8881818	1888111	1111888	8118888	8818181	1818818	1188818	8181188	8811181	1818818	1181881	8188188
1118811	8111118	8888188	1881888	1118881	8118188	8881111	1888818	1188188	8181818	8818881	1811811	1181818	8188881	8811818	1818181
8111881	1118888	1881811	8888118	8118111	1118118	1888888	8881888	8181888	1188181	1811188	8818818	8188818	1181181	1818188	8811881
1881118	8888111	8118888	1118188	1888188	8881888	8118818	1111111	1818181	8818188	8181811	1188881	1818881	8811818	8188181	1181818
8818181	1818188	1188881	8181818	8811181	1818881	1181818	8188188	8888818	1881111	1118188	8118881	8881888	1888188	1111118	8118811
1188181	8181881	8818818	1811181	1181188	8188818	8818818	1818181	1118888	8111888	8888111	1881818	1111811	8118118	8881881	1888888
8181888	1188181	1811818	8818881	8188888	1181811	1818188	8818181	8111111	1118818	1881888	8888188	8118881	1118888	1888811	8881118
1818811	8818181	8181181	1188818	1818818	8811188	8188181	1181881	1881888	8888888	8118118	1118111	1888118	8881811	8118888	1111881
8818188	1818111	1181888	8188888	8818888	1811881	1188118	8181811	8881181	1888818	1118811	8118188	8888181	1881888	1118818	8111188
1181888	8188188	8811111	1818818	1188811	8181118	8818188	1818888	1111818	8118881	8881888	1888181	1118188	8118181	8888888	1881811
8188111	1181818	1818888	8811888	8181881	1188888	1818111	8818118	8118818	1111181	1888188	8881881	8118818	1118181	1881188	8888818
1818188	8818881	8188818	1181111	1811118	8818811	8181888	1188188	1888881	8881818	8118181	1118188	1881818	8888188	8111811	1118888
8881811	1888888	1118181	8118188	8888181	1881818	1118881	8111818	8818888	1818881	1181118	8188811	8818818	1811111	1188188	8181888
1111188	8118818	8881888	1888181	1118188	8118811	8888818	1881181	1181811	8188118	8811881	1818888	1188888	8181888	8818111	1818118
8118888	1111811	1888188	8881818	8111818	1118181	1881818	8888881	8188188	1181888	1818811	8811118	8181111	1188818	1818881	8818188
1888818	8881188	8118181	1118818	1881881	8888188	8111181	1118818	1818118	8818111	8188888	1181881	1811888	8818881	8181818	1188111

The magic and *bimagic* sums of above magic square are $S_{16 \times 16}(1,8) := 799999992$ and $Sb_{16 \times 16}(1,8) := 59797978997979800$. The blocks of order 4 are magic squares with equal magic sums. It is *upside-down* and *mirror-looking*, i.e., *universal* magic square.

Example 4.9. The *bimagic* squares of order 16 for the digits (2,5) is given by

55555555	25522552	22252225	52225222	55525225	25552222	22222555	52255552	55252522	25225525	22555252	52522255	55222252	25255255	22525522	52552525
22255222	52222225	55552552	25525555	22225552	52252555	55522222	25555225	22552255	52525252	55255525	25222522	22522525	52555522	55225255	25252252
52222552	22255555	25525222	55552225	52252222	22225225	25555552	55522555	52525525	22552522	25222255	55255252	52555255	22522252	25252525	55225522
25522225	55555222	52225555	22252552	25552555	55525552	52255225	22222222	25225252	55252255	52522522	22555525	25255522	55222252	25252525	55225522
55252252	25225255	22555522	52522525	55222522	25255525	22525252	52552255	55555225	25522222	22225555	52225552	55525555	25552552	22222225	52255222
22552525	52525522	55255255	25222252	22522255	52555252	55225525	25252522	22255552	52222555	55552222	25525225	22225222	52252225	55522552	25555555
52525255	22552252	25222525	55255522	52555525	22522522	25252255	55225252	52222222	22255225	25525552	55552555	52252552	22225555	25555222	55522225
25225522	55252525	52522252	22555255	25255252	55222255	52552522	22525525	25522555	55555552	52225225	22252222	25552225	55525222	52255555	22222552
55225225	25252222	22522555	52555552	55255555	25222552	22552225	52525222	55522552	25555255	22225522	52252525	55552522	25525525	22255252	52222255
22525552	52552555	55222222	25255225	22555222	52522225	55252552	25225555	22222525	52255522	55525255	25552252	22252255	52225252	55555525	25522522
52552222	22525225	25255552	55222555	52522552	22555555	25225222	55252225	52255255	22222252	25552525	55525522	52225525	22252522	25522255	55555252
25252555	55225552	52555225	22522222	25222225	55255222	52525555	22552552	25555522	55522525	52252252	22225255	25525252	55552255	52222522	22255525
55522522	25555525	22225252	52252255	55552252	25525255	22255522	52222525	55225555	25252552	22522225	52555222	55255225	25222222	22552555	52525552
22222255	52255252	55525525	25552522	22225255	52225522	55555255	25522252	22525222	52552225	55222552	25255555	22555552	52522555	55252222	25225225
52255525	22222522	25552255	55525252	52225255	22225252	25522525	55555522	52552552	22525555	25255222	55222225	52522222	22555225	25225552	55252555
25555252	55522255	52252522	22225525	25525522	55552525	52222252	22255255	25252225	55225222	52555555	22522552	25222555	55255552	52525225	22552222

The magic and *bimagic* sums of above magic square are $S_{16 \times 16}(2,5) := 622222216$ and $Sb_{16 \times 16}(2,5) := 27833894016610552$. The blocks of order 4 are magic squares with equal magic sums. It is *upside-down* and *mirror-looking*, i.e., *universal* magic square.

Example 4.10. The *bimagic* squares of order 16 for the digits (6, 9) is given by

99999999	69966996	66696669	96669666	99969669	69996666	66666999	96699996	99696966	69669969	66999696	96966699	99666696	69699699	66969966	96996969
66699666	96666669	99996996	69969999	66669996	96696999	99966666	69999669	66996699	96969696	99699969	69666966	66966699	96999666	99669699	69696696
96666996	66699999	69969666	99996669	96696666	66669669	69999996	99966999	96969969	66996966	69666699	99699696	96999699	66966696	69696969	99669966
69966669	99999666	96669999	66696996	69996999	99969996	96699669	66666666	69669696	99696699	96966696	66999669	69699666	99666699	96996696	66969699
99696696	69669699	66999666	96966969	99666966	69699699	66969696	96996699	99999669	69966666	66696999	96669996	99969999	69996996	66666669	96699666
66996969	96969666	99699699	69666696	66966699	96999696	99669969	69696966	66699996	96666999	99996666	69969669	66669666	96696669	99966996	69999999
96969699	66996696	69666969	99699966	96999969	66966966	69696699	99669696	96666666	66699669	69969996	99996999	96696996	66669999	69999666	99966669
69669966	99696969	96966696	66999699	69699696	99666699	96996966	66969969	69966999	99999996	96669669	66696666	69996669	99969666	96699999	66666996
99669669	69696666	66966999	96999996	99699999	69666996	66996669	96969666	99966696	69999699	66669966	96696969	99996966	69969969	66699696	96666699
66969996	96996999	99666666	69699669	66999666	96966669	99696996	69669999	66666969	96699966	99969699	69996696	66666699	96669696	99999669	69966966
96996666	66966669	69699996	99666999	96966996	66999999	69669666	99696669	96699699	66666696	69996969	99969966	96669969	66669666	69966699	99999696
69696999	99669996	96999669	66966666	69666669	99699666	96969999	66996996	69999966	99966699	96696966	66669699	69969696	99996699	96666966	66699969
99966966	69999669	66669696	96696699	99996696	69969699	66699966	96666969	99669999	69696996	66966669	96999666	99699669	69666666	66996999	96969996
66666699	96699696	99969969	69996966	66696969	96669966	99999699	69966696	66969666	96996669	99666996	69699999	66999996	96966999	99696666	69669669
96699669	66666966	69996699	99969696	96669699	66696966	69966969	99999666	96996996	66969999	69699666	99666669	96966666	66999669	69669996	99696999
69999696	99966699	96696966	66669969	69969966	99996969	96666696	66699699	69696669	99669666	96999999	66966996	69666999	99699996	96969669	66996666

The magic and *bimagic* sums of above magic square are $S_{16 \times 16}(6, 9) := 1333333320$ and $Sb_{16 \times 16}(6, 9) := 114747472525252536$. The blocks of order 4 are magic squares with equal magic sums. It is only *upside-down*.

4.2 Upside-Down and Mirror Looking with Magic Rectangles

Example 4.11. The magic squares of order 16 formed by magic rectangles of order 2×4 for the digits (1, 8) is given by

11118188 88881818 88881881 11118111	11111888 88888118 88888181 11118111	11818188 88181818 88181881 11818111	11811888 88188118 88188181 11818111
88881811 11118181 11118118 88881888	88888111 11111881 11111818 88888188	88181811 11818181 11818118 88181888	88188111 11811881 11811818 88188188
11111111 88888881 88888818 11111188	11118811 88881181 88881118 11118888	11811111 88188881 88188818 11811188	11818811 88181181 88181118 11818888
88888888 11111118 11111181 88888811	88881188 11118818 11118881 88881111	88188888 11811118 11811181 88188811	88181188 11818818 11818881 88181111
11188111 88811881 88811818 11188188	11181888 88818118 88818181 11181811	11888111 88111881 88111818 11888188	11881888 88118118 88118181 11881811
88811888 11188118 11188181 88811811	88818111 11181881 11181818 88818188	88111888 11888118 11888181 88111811	88118111 11881881 11881818 88118188
11181188 88818818 88818881 11181111	11188811 88811181 88811118 11188888	11881188 88118818 88118881 11881111	11888811 88111181 88111118 11888888
88818811 11181181 11181118 88818888	88811188 11188818 11188881 88811111	88118811 11881181 11881118 88118888	88111188 11888818 11888881 88111111
18118188 81881818 81881881 18118111	18111888 81888118 81888181 18111811	18818188 81181818 81181881 18818111	18811888 81188118 81188181 18811811
81881811 18118181 18118118 81881888	81888111 18111881 18111818 81888188	81181811 18818181 18818118 81181888	81188111 18811881 18811818 81188188
18111111 81888881 81888818 18111188	18118811 81881181 81881118 18118888	18811111 81188881 81188818 18811188	18818811 81181181 81181118 18818888
81888888 18111118 18111181 81888811	81881188 18118818 18118881 81881111	81188888 18811118 18811181 81188811	81181188 18818818 18818881 81181111
18188111 81811881 81811818 18188188	18181888 81818118 81818181 18181811	18888111 81111881 81111818 18888188	18881888 81118118 81118181 18881811
81811888 18188118 18188181 81811811	81818111 18181881 18181818 81818188	81111888 18888118 18888181 81111811	81118111 18881881 18881818 81118188
18181188 81818818 81818881 18181111	18188811 81811181 81811118 18188888	18881188 81118818 81118881 18881111	18888811 81111181 81111118 18888888
81818811 18181181 18181118 81818888	81811188 18188818 18188881 81811111	81118811 18881181 18881118 81118888	81111188 18888818 18888881 81111111

The magic sums of above magic square is $S_{16 \times 16}(1, 8) := 799999992$. The blocks of order 4 are *pandiagonal* magic squares with equal magic sums. It is *upside-down and mirror-looking*, i.e., *universal magic square*. It is also *pandiagonal*.

Example 4.12. The magic squares of order 16 formed by magic rectangles of order 2×4 for the digits (2,5) is given by

22225255	55552525	55552552	22225222	22222555	55555225	55555252	22222522	22525255	55252525	55252552	22525222	22522555	55255225	55255252	22522522
55552522	22225252	22225225	55552555	55555222	22222552	22222525	55555255	55252522	22525252	22525225	55252555	55255222	22522552	22522525	55255255
22222222	55555552	55555525	22222255	22225522	55552252	55552225	22225555	22522222	55255552	55255525	22522255	22525522	55252252	55252225	22525555
55555555	22222225	22222252	55555522	55552255	22225525	22225552	55552222	55255555	22522225	22522252	55255522	55252255	22525525	22525552	55252222
22255222	55522552	55522525	22255255	22252555	55525225	55525252	22252522	22555222	55222552	55222525	22555255	22552555	55225225	55225252	22552522
55522555	22255225	22255252	55522522	55525222	22252552	22252525	55525255	55222555	22555225	22555252	55222522	55225255	22552225	22552252	55225255
22252255	55525525	55525552	22252222	22255522	55522252	55522225	22255555	22552255	55225525	55225552	22552222	22555522	55222252	55222225	22555555
55525522	22252252	22252225	55525555	55522255	22255525	22255552	55522222	55225522	22552252	22552225	55225555	55222255	22555525	22555552	55222222
25225255	52552525	52552552	25225222	25222555	52555225	52555252	25222522	25525255	52252525	52252552	25525222	25522555	52255225	52255252	25522522
52552522	25225252	25225225	52552555	52555222	25222552	25222525	52555255	52252522	25525252	25525225	52252555	52255222	25522552	25522525	52255255
25222222	52555552	52555525	25222255	25225522	52552252	52552225	25225555	25522222	52255552	52255525	25522255	25525522	52252252	52252225	25525555
52555555	25222225	25222252	52555522	52552255	25225525	25225552	52552222	52255555	25522225	25522252	52255522	52252255	25525525	25525552	52252222
25255222	52522552	52522525	25255255	25252555	52525225	52525252	25252522	25555222	52222552	52222525	25555255	25552555	52225225	52225252	25552522
52522555	25255225	25255252	52522522	52525222	25252552	25252525	52525255	52222555	25555225	25555252	52222522	52225255	25552225	25552252	52225255
25252255	52525525	52525552	25252222	25255522	52522252	52522225	25255555	25552255	52225525	52225552	25552222	25555522	52222252	52222225	25555555
52525522	25252252	25252225	52525555	52522255	25255525	25255552	52522222	52225522	25552252	25552225	52225555	52222255	25555525	25555552	52222222

The magic sums of above magic square is $S_{16 \times 16}(2,5) := 622222216$. The blocks of order 4 are *pandiagonal* magic squares with equal magic sums. It is *upside-down* and *mirror-looking*, i.e., *universal* magic square. It is also *pandiagonal*.

Example 4.13. The magic squares of order 16 formed by magic rectangles of order 2×4 for the digits (6,9) is given by

66669699	99996969	99996996	66669666	66666999	99999669	99999696	66666966	66969699	99696969	99696996	66969666	66966999	99699669	99699696	66966966
99996966	66669696	66669669	99996999	99999666	66666996	66666969	99999699	99696966	66969696	66966669	99696999	99699666	66966996	66966969	99699699
66666666	99999996	99999969	66666699	66669966	99996696	99996669	66669999	66966666	99699996	99699969	66966699	66969966	99696696	99696669	66969999
99999999	66666669	66666696	99999966	99996699	66669969	66669996	99996666	99699999	66966669	66966696	99699966	99696699	66966996	66966969	99696666
66699666	99966996	99966969	66699699	66696999	99969669	99969696	66696966	66999666	99666996	99666969	66999699	66996699	99669669	99669696	66996966
99966999	66699669	66699696	99966966	99969666	66696996	66696969	99969699	99666999	66999669	66999696	99666966	99669669	66996699	66996966	99669699
66696699	99969969	99969996	66696666	66699966	99966696	99966669	66699999	66996699	99669969	99669996	66996666	66999966	99666696	99666669	66999999
99969966	66696696	66696669	99969999	99966699	66699969	66699996	99966666	99669966	66996696	66996669	99669999	99666699	66999969	66999996	99666666
69669699	96996969	96996996	69669666	69666999	96999669	96999696	69666966	69969699	96696969	96696996	69969666	69966999	96699669	96699696	69966966
96996966	69669696	69669669	96996999	96999666	69666996	69666969	96999699	96696966	69969696	69969669	96699699	96669666	69966999	69966996	96699699
69666666	96999996	96999969	69666699	69669966	96996696	96996669	69669999	69966666	96699996	96699969	69966699	69969966	96696696	96696669	69969999
96999999	69666669	69666696	96999966	96996699	69669969	69669996	96996666	96699999	69966669	69966696	96699966	96696699	69969966	69969996	96696666
69699666	96966996	96966969	69699699	69696999	96969669	96969696	69696966	69999666	96666996	96666969	69999699	69996699	96669669	96669696	69996966
96966999	69699669	69699696	96966966	96969666	69696996	69696969	96969699	96666999	69999669	69999696	96666966	96669669	69996996	69996969	96669699
69696699	96969969	96969996	69696666	69699966	96966696	96966669	69699999	69996699	96669969	96669996	69996666	69999966	96666696	96666669	69999999
96969966	69696696	69696669	96969999	96966699	69699969	69699996	96966666	96669966	69996696	69996669	96669999	96666699	69999969	69999996	96666666

The magic sums of above magic square is $S_{16 \times 16}(6,9) := 1333333320$. The blocks of order 4 are *pandiagonal* magic squares with equal magic sums. It is only only *upside-down*, It is also *pandiagonal*.

4.3 Water Reflection Magic Squares

Below are few examples of magic square with **water reflection**. These examples are for 4-digits: (2,3,5,8), (1,2,3,5), (0,2,3,5) and (0,1,3,8) with **water reflection** property.

Example 4.14. Let's consider a magic square of order 16 with 4-digits (2,3,5,8) given by

2222	5353	8585	3838	2335	5288	8852	3523	2558	5825	8233	3382	2883	5532	8328	3255
8538	3885	2253	5322	8823	3552	2388	5235	8282	3333	2525	5858	8355	3228	2832	5583
3853	8522	5338	2285	3588	8835	5223	2352	3325	8258	5882	2533	3232	8383	5555	2828
5385	2238	3822	8553	5252	2323	3535	8888	5833	2582	3358	8225	5528	2855	3283	8332
2583	5832	8228	3355	2858	5525	8333	3282	2235	5388	8552	3823	2322	5253	8885	3538
8255	3328	2532	5883	8382	3233	2825	5558	8523	3852	2288	5335	8838	3585	2353	5222
3332	8283	5855	2528	3225	8358	5582	2833	3888	8535	5323	2252	3553	8822	5238	2385
5828	2555	3383	8232	5533	2882	3258	8325	5352	2223	3835	8588	5285	2338	3522	8853
2835	5588	8352	3223	2522	5853	8285	3338	2383	5232	8828	3555	2258	5325	8533	3882
8323	3252	2888	5535	8238	3385	2553	5822	8855	3528	2332	5283	8582	3833	2225	5358
3288	8335	5523	2852	3353	8222	5838	2585	3532	8883	5255	2328	3825	8558	5382	2233
5552	2823	3235	8388	5885	2538	3322	8253	5228	2355	3583	8832	5333	2282	3858	8525
2358	5225	8833	3582	2283	5332	8528	3855	2822	5553	8385	3238	2535	5888	8252	3323
8882	3533	2325	5258	8555	3828	2232	5383	8338	3285	2853	5522	8223	3352	2588	5835
3525	8858	5282	2333	3832	8583	5355	2228	3253	8322	5538	2885	3388	8235	5823	2552
5233	2382	3558	8825	5328	2255	3883	8532	5585	2838	3222	8353	5852	2523	3335	8288

The above magic squares is **bimagic**. The magic sums are $S_{16 \times 16}(2, 3, 5, 8) = 79992$ and $Sb_{16 \times 16}(2, 3, 5, 8) = 484768488$. The blocks of order 4 are magic squares with equal magic sums, i.e., $S_{4 \times 4}(2, 3, 5, 8) = 19998$.

• **Water Reflection**

Applying the **vertical flip** over the above magic square, we get

2533	5385	3228	8852	2358	5522	3883	8235	2282	5838	3555	8323	2825	5253	3332	8588
3252	8828	2585	5333	3835	8283	2322	5558	3523	8355	2238	5882	3388	8532	2853	5225
8885	3233	5352	2528	8222	3858	5535	2383	8338	3582	5823	2255	8553	3325	5288	2832
5328	2552	8833	3285	5583	2335	8258	3822	5855	2223	8382	3538	5232	2888	8525	3353
2225	5853	3532	8388	2882	5238	3355	8523	2558	5322	3283	8835	2333	5585	3828	8252
3588	8332	2253	5825	3323	8555	2838	5282	3235	8883	2522	5358	3852	8228	2385	5533
8353	3525	5888	2232	8538	3382	5223	2855	8822	3258	5335	2583	8285	3833	5552	2328
5832	2288	8325	3553	5255	2823	8582	3338	5383	2535	8858	3222	5528	2352	8233	3885
2858	5222	3383	8535	2233	5885	3528	8352	2325	5553	3832	8288	2582	5338	3255	8823
3335	8583	2822	5258	3552	8328	2285	5833	3888	8232	2353	5525	3223	8855	2538	5382
8522	3358	5235	2883	8385	3533	5852	2228	8253	3825	5588	2332	8838	3282	5323	2555
5283	2835	8558	3322	5828	2252	8333	3585	5532	2388	8225	3853	5355	2523	8882	3238
2382	5538	3855	8223	2525	5353	3232	8888	2833	5285	3328	8552	2258	5822	3583	8335
3823	8255	2338	5582	3288	8832	2553	5325	3352	8528	2885	5233	3535	8383	2222	5858
8238	3882	5523	2355	8853	3225	5388	2532	8585	3333	5252	2828	8322	3558	5835	2283
5555	2323	8282	3838	5332	2588	8825	3253	5228	2852	8533	3385	5883	2235	8358	3522

Thus, the above magic square of order 16 with digits is (2,3,5,8) is **water reflexive** and **bimagic**. The magic sums are $S_{16 \times 16}(2,3,5,8) = 79992$ and $Sb_{16 \times 16}(2,3,5,8) = 484768488$. The blocks of order 4 are magic squares with equal magic sums, i.e., $S_{4 \times 4}(2,3,5,8) = 19998$. Let's see below few more examples.

Example 4.15. Let's replace 8 by 1 in Example 4.14, we get

2222	5353	1515	3131	2335	5211	1152	3523	2551	5125	1233	3312	2113	5532	1321	3255
1531	3115	2253	5322	1123	3552	2311	5235	1212	3333	2525	5151	1355	3221	2132	5513
3153	1522	5331	2215	3511	1135	5223	2352	3325	1251	5112	2533	3232	1313	5555	2121
5315	2231	3122	1553	5252	2323	3535	1111	5133	2512	3351	1225	5521	2155	3213	1332
2513	5132	1221	3355	2151	5525	1333	3212	2235	5311	1552	3123	2322	5253	1115	3531
1255	3321	2532	5113	1312	3233	2125	5551	1523	3152	2211	5335	1131	3515	2353	5222
3332	1213	5155	2521	3225	1351	5512	2133	3111	1535	5323	2252	3553	1122	5231	2315
5121	2555	3313	1232	5533	2112	3251	1325	5352	2223	3135	1511	5215	2331	3522	1153
2135	5511	1352	3223	2522	5153	1215	3331	2313	5232	1121	3555	2251	5325	1533	3112
1323	3252	2111	5535	1231	3315	2553	5122	1155	3521	2332	5213	1512	3133	2225	5351
3211	1335	5523	2152	3353	1222	5131	2515	3532	1113	5255	2321	3125	1551	5312	2233
5552	2123	3235	1311	5115	2531	3322	1253	5221	2355	3513	1132	5333	2212	3151	1525
2351	5225	1133	3512	2213	5332	1521	3155	2122	5553	1315	3231	2535	5111	1252	3323
1112	3533	2325	5251	1555	3121	2232	5313	1331	3215	2153	5522	1223	3352	2511	5135
3525	1151	5212	2333	3132	1513	5355	2221	3253	1322	5531	2115	3311	1235	5123	2552
5233	2312	3551	1125	5321	2255	3113	1532	5515	2131	3222	1353	5152	2523	3335	1211

It is **bimagic** square. The magic sums are $S_{16 \times 16}(1, 2, 3, 5) = 48884$ and $Sb_{16 \times 16}(1, 2, 3, 5) = 184706376$. The blocks of order 4 are magic squares with equal magic sums, i.e., $S_{4 \times 4}(1, 2, 3, 5) = 12221$.

• **Water Reflection**

Applying the vertical flip over the above magic square, we get

2533	5315	3221	1152	2351	5522	3113	1235	2212	5131	3555	1323	2125	5253	3332	1511
3252	1121	2515	5333	3135	1213	2322	5551	3523	1355	2231	5112	3311	1532	2153	5225
1115	3233	5352	2521	1222	3151	5535	2313	1331	3512	5123	2255	1553	3325	5211	2132
5321	2552	1133	3215	5513	2335	1251	3122	5155	2223	1312	3531	5232	2111	1525	3353
2225	5153	3532	1311	2112	5231	3355	1523	2551	5322	3213	1135	2333	5515	3121	1252
3511	1332	2253	5125	3323	1555	2131	5212	3235	1113	2522	5351	3152	1221	2315	5533
1353	3525	5111	2232	1531	3312	5223	2155	1122	3251	5335	2513	1215	3133	5552	2321
5132	2211	1325	3553	5255	2123	1512	3331	5313	2535	1151	3222	5521	2352	1233	3115
2151	5222	3313	1535	2233	5115	3521	1352	2325	5553	3132	1211	2512	5331	3255	1123
3335	1513	2122	5251	3552	1321	2215	5133	3111	1232	2353	5525	3223	1155	2531	5312
1522	3351	5235	2113	1315	3533	5152	2221	1253	3125	5511	2332	1131	3212	5323	2555
5213	2135	1551	3322	5121	2252	1333	3515	5532	2311	1225	3153	5355	2523	1112	3231
2312	5531	3155	1223	2525	5353	3232	1111	2133	5215	3321	1552	2251	5122	3513	1335
3123	1255	2331	5512	3211	1132	2553	5325	3352	1521	2115	5233	3535	1313	2222	5151
1231	3112	5523	2355	1153	3225	5311	2532	1515	3333	5252	2121	1322	3551	5135	2213
5555	2323	1212	3131	5332	2511	1125	3253	5221	2152	1533	3315	5113	2235	1351	3522

It is **bimagic** square. The magic sums are $S_{16 \times 16}(1, 2, 3, 5) = 48884$ and $Sb_{16 \times 16}(1, 2, 3, 5) = 184706376$. The blocks of order 4 are magic squares with equal magic sums, i.e., $S_{4 \times 4}(1, 2, 3, 5) = 12221$.

Thus, the above magic square is **water reflexive** with equal magic sums. The blocks of order 4 are magic squares with equal magic sums.

Example 4.16. Let's replace 1 by 0 in Example 4.15, we get

2222	5353	0505	3030	2335	5200	0052	3523	2550	5025	0233	3302	2003	5532	0320	3255
0530	3005	2253	5322	0023	3552	2300	5235	0202	3333	2525	5050	0355	3220	2032	5503
3053	0522	5330	2205	3500	0035	5223	2352	3325	0250	5002	2533	3232	0303	5555	2020
5305	2230	3022	0553	5252	2323	3535	0000	5033	2502	3350	0225	5520	2055	3203	0332
2503	5032	0220	3355	2050	5525	0333	3202	2235	5300	0552	3023	2322	5253	0005	3530
0255	3320	2532	5003	0302	3233	2025	5550	0523	3052	2200	5335	0030	3505	2353	5222
3332	0203	5055	2520	3225	0350	5502	2033	3000	0535	5323	2252	3553	0022	5230	2305
5020	2555	3303	0232	5533	2002	3250	0325	5352	2223	3035	0500	5205	2330	3522	0053
2035	5500	0352	3223	2522	5053	0205	3330	2303	5232	0020	3555	2250	5325	0533	3002
0323	3252	2000	5535	0230	3305	2553	5022	0055	3520	2332	5203	0502	3033	2225	5350
3200	0335	5523	2052	3353	0222	5030	2505	3532	0003	5255	2320	3025	0550	5302	2233
5552	2023	3235	0300	5005	2530	3322	0253	5220	2355	3503	0032	5333	2202	3050	0525
2350	5225	0033	3502	2203	5332	0520	3055	2022	5553	0305	3230	2535	5000	0252	3323
0002	3533	2325	5250	0555	3020	2232	5303	0330	3205	2053	5522	0223	3352	2500	5035
3525	0050	5202	2333	3032	0503	5355	2220	3253	0322	5530	2005	3300	0235	5023	2552
5233	2302	3550	0025	5320	2255	3003	0532	5505	2030	3222	0353	5052	2523	3335	0200

It is **bimagic** square. The magic sums are $S_{16 \times 16}(0, 2, 3, 5) = 44440$ and $Sb_{16 \times 16}(0, 2, 3, 5) = 175957352$. The blocks of order 4 are magic squares with equal magic sums, i.e., $S_{4 \times 4}(0, 2, 3, 5) = 11110$.

• **Water Reflection**

Applying the vertical flip over the above magic square, we get

2533	5305	3220	0052	2350	5522	3003	0235	2202	5030	3555	0323	2025	5253	3332	0500
3252	0020	2505	5333	3035	0203	2322	5550	3523	0355	2230	5002	3300	0532	2053	5225
0005	3233	5352	2520	0222	3050	5535	2303	0330	3502	5023	2255	0553	3325	5200	2032
5320	2552	0033	3205	5503	2335	0250	3022	5055	2223	0302	3530	5232	2000	0525	3353
2225	5053	3532	0300	2002	5230	3355	0523	2550	5322	3203	0035	2333	5505	3020	0252
3500	0332	2253	5025	3323	0555	2030	5202	3235	0003	2522	5350	3052	0220	2305	5533
0353	3525	5000	2232	0530	3302	5223	2055	0022	3250	5335	2503	0205	3033	5552	2320
5032	2200	0325	3553	5255	2023	0502	3330	5303	2535	0050	3222	5520	2352	0233	3005
2050	5222	3303	0535	2233	5005	3520	0352	2325	5553	3032	0200	2502	5330	3255	0023
3335	0503	2022	5250	3552	0320	2205	5033	3000	0232	2353	5525	3223	0055	2530	5302
0522	3350	5235	2003	0305	3533	5052	2220	0253	3025	5500	2332	0030	3202	5323	2555
5203	2035	0550	3322	5020	2252	0333	3505	5532	2300	0225	3053	5355	2523	0002	3230
2302	5530	3055	0223	2525	5353	3232	0000	2033	5205	3320	0552	2250	5022	3503	0335
3023	0255	2330	5502	3200	0032	2553	5325	3352	0520	2005	5233	3535	0303	2222	5050
0230	3002	5523	2355	0053	3225	5300	2532	0505	3333	5252	2020	0322	3550	5035	2203
5555	2323	0202	3030	5332	2500	0025	3253	5220	2052	0533	3305	5003	2235	0350	3522

It is **bimagic** square. The magic sums are $S_{16 \times 16}(0, 2, 3, 5) = 44440$ and $Sb_{16 \times 16}(0, 2, 3, 5) = 175957352$. The blocks of order 4 are magic squares with equal magic sums, i.e., $S_{4 \times 4}(0, 2, 3, 5) = 11110$.

Example 4.17. Let's replace 2 by 1 and 5 by 8 in Example 4.16, we get

1111	8383	0808	3030	1338	8100	0081	3813	1880	8018	0133	3301	1003	8831	0310	3188
0830	3008	1183	8311	0013	3881	1300	8138	0101	3333	1818	8080	0388	3110	1031	8803
3083	0811	8330	1108	3800	0038	8113	1381	3318	0180	8001	1833	3131	0303	8888	1010
8308	1130	3011	0883	8181	1313	3838	0000	8033	1801	3380	0118	8810	1088	3103	0331
1803	8031	0110	3388	1080	8818	0333	3101	1138	8300	0881	3013	1311	8183	0008	3830
0188	3310	1831	8003	0301	3133	1018	8880	0813	3081	1100	8338	0030	3808	1383	8111
3331	0103	8088	1810	3118	0380	8801	1033	3000	0838	8313	1181	3883	0011	8130	1308
8010	1888	3303	0131	8833	1001	3180	0318	8381	1113	3038	0800	8108	1330	3811	0083
1038	8800	0381	3113	1811	8083	0108	3330	1303	8131	0010	3888	1180	8318	0833	3001
0313	3181	1000	8838	0130	3308	1883	8011	0088	3810	1331	8103	0801	3033	1118	8380
3100	0338	8813	1081	3383	0111	8030	1808	3831	0003	8188	1310	3018	0880	8301	1133
8881	1013	3138	0300	8008	1830	3311	0183	8110	1388	3803	0031	8333	1101	3080	0818
1380	8118	0033	3801	1103	8331	0810	3088	1011	8883	0308	3130	1838	8000	0181	3313
0001	3833	1318	8180	0888	3010	1131	8303	0330	3108	1083	8811	0113	3381	1800	8038
3818	0080	8101	1333	3031	0803	8388	1110	3183	0311	8830	1008	3300	0138	8013	1881
8133	1301	3880	0018	8310	1188	3003	0831	8808	1030	3111	0383	8081	1813	3338	0100

It is **bimagic** square. The magic sums are $S_{16 \times 16}(0, 1, 3, 8) = 53328$ and $Sb_{16 \times 16}(0, 1, 3, 8) = 331277576$. The blocks of order 4 are magic squares with equal magic sums, i.e., $S_{4 \times 4}(0, 1, 3, 8) = 13332$.

• **Water Reflection**

Applying the vertical flip over the above magic square, we get

1111	8383	0808	3030	1338	8100	0081	3813	1880	8018	0133	3301	1003	8831	0310	3188
0830	3008	1183	8311	0013	3881	1300	8138	0101	3333	1818	8080	0388	3110	1031	8803
3083	0811	8330	1108	3800	0038	8113	1381	3318	0180	8001	1833	3131	0303	8888	1010
8308	1130	3011	0883	8181	1313	3838	0000	8033	1801	3380	0118	8810	1088	3103	0331
1803	8031	0110	3388	1080	8818	0333	3101	1138	8300	0881	3013	1311	8183	0008	3830
0188	3310	1831	8003	0301	3133	1018	8880	0813	3081	1100	8338	0030	3808	1383	8111
3331	0103	8088	1810	3118	0380	8801	1033	3000	0838	8313	1181	3883	0011	8130	1308
8010	1888	3303	0131	8833	1001	3180	0318	8381	1113	3038	0800	8108	1330	3811	0083
1038	8800	0381	3113	1811	8083	0108	3330	1303	8131	0010	3888	1180	8318	0833	3001
0313	3181	1000	8838	0130	3308	1883	8011	0088	3810	1331	8103	0801	3033	1118	8380
3100	0338	8813	1081	3383	0111	8030	1808	3831	0003	8188	1310	3018	0880	8301	1133
8881	1013	3138	0300	8008	1830	3311	0183	8110	1388	3803	0031	8333	1101	3080	0818
1380	8118	0033	3801	1103	8331	0810	3088	1011	8883	0308	3130	1838	8000	0181	3313
0001	3833	1318	8180	0888	3010	1131	8303	0330	3108	1083	8811	0113	3381	1800	8038
3818	0080	8101	1333	3031	0803	8388	1110	3183	0311	8830	1008	3300	0138	8013	1881
8133	1301	3880	0018	8310	1188	3003	0831	8808	1030	3111	0383	8081	1813	3338	0100

it is **bimagic** square. The magic sums are $S_{16 \times 16}(0, 1, 3, 8) = 53328$ and $Sb_{16 \times 16}(0, 1, 3, 8) = 331277576$. The blocks of order 4 are magic squares with equal magic sums, i.e., $S_{4 \times 4}(0, 1, 3, 8) = 13332$.

Finally, we have four **bimagic** squares of order 16 with 4-digits (2,3,5,8), (1,2,3,5), (0,2,3,5) and (0,1,3,8) having **water reflection** property with same magic and **bimagic** sums. The blocks of order 4 are magic squares with equal magic sums.

For more studied with different options, see the author's work [46, 47].

4.4 Self-Made Algebraic Magic Square

Below is a result of a magic square order 16 made from the variables A1 to A96 in such a way that blocks of order 4 are equal sums magic squares of order 4.

Result 1. Below is an algebraic magic square of order 16

A1	A4+S-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	A7	A10+S-A12-A7	A12-A9-A10	A9	A13	A16+S-A18-A13	A18-A15-A16	A15	A19	A22+S-A24-A19	A24-A21-A22	A21
A6	A4	A5	S-A4-A5-A6	A12	A10	A11	S-A10-A11-A12	A18	A16	A17	S-A16-A17-A18	A24	A22	A23	S-A22-A23-A24
A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	S-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	A8+A9-A12	A7+A8-A11	S-A7-A8-A10	A10+A11+A12-A8-A9	A14+A15-A18	A13+A14-A17	S-A13-A14-A16	A16+A17+A18-A14-A15	A20+A21-A24	A19+A20-A23	S-A19-A20-A22	A22+A23+A24-A20-A21
S-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6	A2	S-A7-A8-A9	A11-A8-2*A10+A12	A7+A8+A9+2*A10-A11-A12	A8	S-A13-A14-A15	A17-A14-2*A16+A18	A13+A14+A15+2*A16-A17-A18	A14	S-A19-A20-A21	A23-A20-2*A22+A24	A19+A20+A21+2*A22-A23-A24	A20
A25	A28+S-A30-A25	A30-A27-A28	A27	A31	A34+S-A36-A31	A36-A33-A34	A33	A37	A40+S-A42-A37	A42-A39-A40	A39	A43	A46+S-A48-A43	A48-A45-A46	A45
A30	A28	A29	S-A28-A29-A30	A36	A34	A35	S-A34-A35-A36	A42	A40	A41	S-A40-A41-A42	A48	A46	A47	S-A46-A47-A48
A26+A27-A30	A25+A26-A29	S-A25-A26-A28	A28+A29+A30-A26-A27	A32+A33-A36	A31+A32-A35	S-A31-A32-A34	A34+A35+A36-A32-A33	A38+A39-A42	A37+A38-A41	S-A37-A38-A40	A40+A41+A42-A38-A39	A44+A45-A48	A43+A44-A47	S-A43-A44-A46	A46+A47+A48-A44-A45
S-A25-A26-A27	A29-A26-2*A28+A30	A25+A26+A27+2*A28-A29-A30	A26	S-A31-A32-A33	A35-A32-2*A34+A36	A31+A32+A33+2*A34-A35-A36	A32	S-A37-A38-A39	A41-A38-2*A40+A42	A37+A38+A39+2*A40-A41-A42	A38	S-A43-A44-A45	A47-A44-2*A46+A48	A43+A44+A45+2*A46-A47-A48	A44
A49	A52+S-A54-A49	A54-A51-A52	A51	A55	A58+S-A60-A55	A60-A57-A58	A57	A61	A64+S-A66-A61	A66-A63-A64	A63	A67	A70+S-A72-A67	A72-A69-A70	A69
A54	A52	A53	S-A52-A53-A54	A60	A58	A59	S-A58-A59-A60	A66	A64	A65	S-A64-A65-A66	A72	A70	A71	S-A70-A71-A72
A50+A51-A54	A49+A50-A53	S-A49-A50-A52	A52+A53+A54-A50-A51	A56+A57-A60	A55+A56-A59	S-A55-A56-A58	A58+A59+A60-A56-A57	A62+A63-A66	A61+A62-A65	S-A61-A62-A64	A64+A65+A66-A62-A63	A68+A69-A72	A67+A68-A71	S-A67-A68-A70	A70+A71+A72-A68-A69
S-A49-A50-A51	A53-A50-2*A52+A54	A49+A50+A51+2*A52-A53-A54	A50	S-A55-A56-A57	A59-A56-2*A58+A60	A55+A56+A57+2*A58-A59-A60	A56	S-A61-A62-A63	A65-A62-2*A64+A66	A61+A62+A63+2*A64-A65-A66	A62	S-A67-A68-A69	A71-A68-2*A70+A72	A67+A68+A69+2*A70-A71-A72	A68
A73	A76+S-A78-A73	A78-A75-A76	A75	A79	A82+S-A84-A79	A84-A81-A82	A81	A85	A88+S-A90-A85	A90-A87-A88	A87	A91	A94+S-A96-A91	A96-A93-A94	A93
A78	A76	A77	S-A76-A77-A78	A84	A82	A83	S-A82-A83-A84	A90	A88	A89	S-A88-A89-A90	A96	A94	A95	S-A94-A95-A96
A74+A75-A78	A73+A74-A77	S-A73-A74-A76	A76+A77+A78-A74-A75	A80+A81-A84	A79+A80-A83	S-A79-A80-A82	A82+A83+A84-A80-A81	A86+A87-A90	A85+A86-A89	S-A85-A86-A88	A88+A89+A90-A86-A87	A92+A93-A96	A91+A92-A95	S-A91-A92-A94	A94+A95+A96-A92-A93
S-A73-A74-A75	A77-A74-2*A76+A78	A73+A74+A75+2*A76-A77-A78	A74	S-A79-A80-A81	A83-A80-2*A82+A84	A79+A80+A81+2*A82-A83-A84	A80	S-A85-A86-A87	A89-A86-2*A88+A90	A85+A86+A87+2*A88-A89-A90	A86	S-A91-A92-A93	A95-A92-2*A94+A96	A91+A92+A93+2*A94-A95-A96	A92

● **Details**

It is constructed in such a way that each block of order 4 are magic square of order 4. The letter *S* represents the sum of each block of order 4. The magic sum of order 16 is $4 \times S$. We call it a **self-made** as choosing any numbers for *A1* to *A96* and the magic sum *S*, we always get a magic square of order 16. Sometimes we may call it as **algebraic magic square for reduced entries**. It requires only 96 entries instead of 256. See below two examples:

Example 4.18. Let's consider a following magic square based on the Result 1

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT															168
2	38	-2	4	8	32	-8	10	14	26	-14	16	20	20	-20	22	168
7	5	6	24	13	11	12	6	19	17	18	-12	25	23	24	-30	168
0	-1	32	11	6	5	14	17	12	11	-4	23	18	17	-22	29	168
33	0	6	3	15	-6	24	9	-3	-12	42	15	-21	-18	60	21	168
26	14	-26	28	32	8	-32	34	38	2	-38	40	44	-4	-44	46	168
31	29	30	-48	37	35	36	-66	43	41	42	-84	49	47	48	-102	168
24	23	-40	35	30	29	-58	41	36	35	-76	47	42	41	-94	53	168
-39	-24	78	27	-57	-30	96	33	-75	-36	114	39	-93	-42	132	45	168
50	-10	-50	52	56	-16	-56	58	62	-22	-62	64	68	-28	-68	70	168
55	53	54	-120	61	59	60	-138	67	65	66	-156	73	71	72	-174	168
48	47	-112	59	54	53	-130	65	60	59	-148	71	66	65	-166	77	168
-111	-48	150	51	-129	-54	168	57	-147	-60	186	63	-165	-66	204	69	168
74	-34	-74	76	80	-40	-80	82	86	-46	-86	88	92	-52	-92	94	168
79	77	78	-192	85	83	84	-210	91	89	90	-228	97	95	96	-246	168
72	71	-184	83	78	77	-202	89	84	83	-220	95	90	89	-238	101	168
-183	-72	222	75	-201	-78	240	81	-219	-84	258	87	-237	-90	276	93	168
168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168

Each block of order 4 is a magic square of order 4 with magic sum $S_{4 \times 4} := 42$ resulting in magic sum of order 16 as $S_{16 \times 16} := 168$.

Example 4.19. *Let's consider a following magic square based on the Result 1*

mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														188	
2	43	-2	4	8	37	-8	10	14	31	-14	16	20	25	-20	22	188
7	5	6	29	13	11	12	11	19	17	18	-7	25	23	24	-25	188
0	-1	37	11	6	5	19	17	12	11	1	23	18	17	-17	29	188
38	0	6	3	20	-6	24	9	2	-12	42	15	-16	-18	60	21	188
26	19	-26	28	32	13	-32	34	38	7	-38	40	44	1	-44	46	188
31	29	30	-43	37	35	36	-61	43	41	42	-79	49	47	48	-97	188
24	23	-35	35	30	29	-53	41	36	35	-71	47	42	41	-89	53	188
-34	-24	78	27	-52	-30	96	33	-70	-36	114	39	-88	-42	132	45	188
50	-5	-50	52	56	-11	-56	58	62	-17	-62	64	68	-23	-68	70	188
55	53	54	-115	61	59	60	-133	67	65	66	-151	73	71	72	-169	188
48	47	-107	59	54	53	-125	65	60	59	-143	71	66	65	-161	77	188
-106	-48	150	51	-124	-54	168	57	-142	-60	186	63	-160	-66	204	69	188
74	-29	-74	76	80	-35	-80	82	86	-41	-86	88	92	-47	-92	94	188
79	77	78	-187	85	83	84	-205	91	89	90	-223	97	95	96	-241	188
72	71	-179	83	78	77	-197	89	84	83	-215	95	90	89	-233	101	188
-178	-72	222	75	-196	-78	240	81	-214	-84	258	87	-232	-90	276	93	188
188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188

Each block of order 4 is a magic square of order 4 with magic sum $S_{4 \times 4} := 47$ resulting in magic sum of order 16 as $S_{16 \times 16} := 188$.

For more studied toward this direction see the author's work [57, 58, 59, 60, 61, 62, 63, 64].

4.5 Double-Digit Algebraic Striped Magic Squares of Order 16

Below are three different ways of writing magic square of order 16, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** and **cornered**.

4.5.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 2. *An algebraic striped magic square of order 16 in cyclic way is given by*

a59	a60	a61	a62	a63	a64	a65	a66	a67	a68	a69	a70	a71	7*m-a62-a63-a64-a65-a66-a67-a68-a69-a70-a71-a61-a59-a60	m-a72	a72
m-a59	m-a60	m-a61	m-a62	m-a63	m-a64	m-a65	m-a66	m-a67	m-a68	m-a69	m-a70	m-a71	a62+a63+a64+a65+a66+a67+a68+a69+a70+a71+a61+a59+a60-6*m	m-a73	a73
7*m-a99-a98-2*a97+a72-a73-a101-a105-a104-a103-a102-a108-a107-a106-a100	a99+a98+2*a97-a72+a73+a101+a105+a104+a103+a102+a108+a107+a106+a100-6*m	a25	a26	a27	a28	a29	a30	a31	a32	a33	5*m-a25-a26-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32-a33	m-a34	a34	m-a74	a74
a108	m-a108	m-a25	m-a26	m-a27	m-a28	m-a29	m-a30	m-a31	m-a32	m-a33	a25+a26+a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32+a33-4*m	m-a35	a35	m-a75	a75
a107	m-a107	5*m-a58-a57-a56-a55-a54-a53-a52-2*a51+a34-a35	a58+a57+a56+a55+a54+a53+a52+2*a51-a34+a35-4*m	a7	a8	a9	a10	a11	3*m-a7-a8-a9-a10-a11	m-a12	a12	m-a36	a36	m-a76	a76
a106	m-a106	a58	m-a58	m-a7	m-a8	m-a9	m-a10	m-a11	a7+a8+a9+a10+a11-2*m	m-a13	a13	m-a37	a37	m-a77	a77
a105	m-a105	a57	m-a57	3*m-a24-a23-a22-2*a21+a12-a13	a24+a23+a22+2*a21-a12+a13-2*m	a4-2*a2-a3+2*m-a1	a1	a2	a2+a3-a4	m-a14	a14	m-a38	a38	m-a78	a78
a104	m-a104	a56	m-a56	a24	m-a24	a1-a4+2*a2+a3-m	m-a1	m-a2	a4-a2-a3+m	m-a15	a15	m-a39	a39	m-a79	a79
a103	m-a103	a55	m-a55	a23	m-a23	a3	a4	a1-a4+a2	2*m-a3-a1-a2	m-a16	a16	m-a40	a40	m-a80	a80
a102	m-a102	a54	m-a54	a22	m-a22	m-a3	m-a4	m-a1+a4-a2	a3+a1+a2-m	a12+a13+a14+a15+a16-2*m	3*m-a12-a13-a14-a15-a16	m-a41	a41	m-a81	a81
a101	m-a101	a53	m-a53	a21	m-a21	a20+a19+a18+2*a17-a7+a8-2*m	m-a20	m-a19	m-a18	m-a17	m+a7-a8-a17	m-a42	a42	m-a82	a82
a100	m-a100	a52	m-a52	a13+a21-a12	m+a12-a13-a21	3*m-a20-a19-a18-2*a17+a7-a8	a20	a19	a18	a17	a8+a17-a7	a34+a35+a36+a37+a38+a39+a40+a41+a42-4*m	5*m-a34-a35-a36-a37-a38-a39-a40-a41-a42	m-a83	a83
a99	m-a99	a51	m-a51	a50+a49+a48+a47+a46+a45+a44+2*a43-a25+a26-4*m	m-a50	m-a49	m-a48	m-a47	m-a46	m-a45	m-a44	m-a43	m+a25-a26-a43	m-a84	a84
a98	m-a98	a35+a51-a34	m+a34-a35-a51	5*m-a50-a49-a48-a47-a46-a45-a44-2*a43+a25-a26	a50	a49	a48	a47	a46	a45	a44	a43	a26+a43-a25	a72+a74+a73+a75+a84+a82+a83+a81+a77+a76+a78+a80+a79-6*m	7*m-a72-a74-a73-a75-a84-a82-a83-a81-a77-a76-a78-a80-a79
a97	m-a97	a96+a88+a87+2*a85+a86+a95+a94+a93+a92+a91+a90+a89-a59+a60-6*m	m-a96	m-a95	m-a94	m-a93	m-a92	m-a91	m-a90	m-a89	m-a88	m-a87	m-a86	m-a85	m+a59-a60-a85
a73+a97-a72	m+a72-a73-a97	7*m-a96-a88-a87-2*a85-a86-a95-a94-a93-a92-a91-a90-a89+a59-a60	a96	a95	a94	a93	a92	a91	a90	a89	a88	a87	a86	a85	a60+a85-a59

● Details

It is an **algebraic cyclic striped** magic square of order 16 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×14 embedded with a magic square of order 12. It is again composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×10 embedded with a magic square of order 8. It is again composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×6 embedded with a magic square of order 4. This magic square of order 4 is with equal sums two magic rectangles of order 2×4 . In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 6m$ and $S_{16 \times 16} := 8m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below two examples:

Example 4.20. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 16 based on Result 2 are given by

16	mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														872	
	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	-82	37	72	872
	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	42	41	40	39	38	191	36	73	872
	-565	674	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	284	75	34	35	74	872
	108	1	84	83	82	81	80	79	78	77	76	-175	74	35	34	75	872
	107	2	57	52	7	8	9	10	11	282	97	12	73	36	33	76	872
	106	3	58	51	102	101	100	99	98	-173	96	13	72	37	32	77	872
	105	4	57	52	215	-106	214	1	2	1	95	14	71	38	31	78	872
	104	5	56	53	24	85	-105	108	107	108	94	15	70	39	30	79	872
	103	6	55	54	23	86	3	4	-1	212	93	16	69	40	29	80	872
	102	7	54	55	22	87	106	105	110	-103	-148	257	68	41	28	81	872
	101	8	53	56	21	88	-126	89	90	91	92	91	67	42	27	82	872
	100	9	52	57	22	87	235	20	19	18	17	18	-94	203	26	83	872
	99	10	51	58	-20	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	65	25	84	872
	98	11	52	57	129	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	44	360	-251	872
	97	12	518	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	23	872
	98	11	-409	96	95	94	93	92	91	90	89	88	87	86	85	86	872
	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872

16	mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/												https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/		©IJT	976
	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	9	50	72	976
	63	62	61	60	59	58	57	56	55	54	53	52	51	113	49	73	976
	-474	596	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	349	88	34	48	74	976
	108	14	97	96	95	94	93	92	91	90	89	-227	87	35	47	75	976
	107	15	122	0	7	8	9	10	11	321	110	12	86	36	46	76	976
	106	16	58	64	115	114	113	112	111	-199	109	13	85	37	45	77	976
	105	17	57	65	254	-132	240	1	2	1	108	14	84	38	44	78	976
	104	18	56	66	24	98	-118	121	120	121	107	15	83	39	43	79	976
	103	19	55	67	23	99	3	4	-1	238	106	16	82	40	42	80	976
	102	20	54	68	22	100	119	118	123	-116	-174	296	81	41	41	81	976
	101	21	53	69	21	101	-152	102	103	104	105	104	80	42	40	82	976
	100	22	52	70	22	100	274	20	19	18	17	18	-146	268	39	83	976
	99	23	51	71	-72	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79	78	38	84	976
	98	24	52	70	194	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	44	282	-160	976
	97	25	440	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	36	976
	98	24	-318	96	95	94	93	92	91	90	89	88	87	86	85	86	976
	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

(i) *First Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 218, S_{8 \times 8} := 436, S_{12 \times 12} := 654, S_{16 \times 16} := 872$ and $m := 109$.

(ii) *Second Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 244, S_{8 \times 8} := 488, S_{12 \times 12} := 732, S_{16 \times 16} := 976$ and $m := 122$.

4.5.2 Flat-Type

Result 3. *An algebraic striped magic square of order 16 in flat way is given by*

a57	a58	a59	a60	a61	a62	a63	a64	a65	a66	a67	a68	a69	8*m-a62-a63-a64-a65-a66-a67-a68-2*a69-a70-a61-a59-a60-a57-a58	a69	a70
m-a57	m-a58	m-a59	m-a60	m-a61	m-a62	m-a63	m-a64	m-a65	m-a66	m-a67	m-a68	m-a69	a62+a63+a64+a65+a66+a67+a68+2*a69+a70+a61+a59+a60+a57+a58-7*m	m-a69	m-a70
6*m-a105-a104-a103-a102-a101-a100-a99-a98-a97-a96-a95	a105+a104+a103+a102+a101+a100+a99+a98+a97+a96+a95-5*m	a23	a24	a25	a26	a27	a28	a29	a30	a31	6*m-a23-a24-a25-a26-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32-a33	a32	a33	m-a71	a71
a105	m-a105	m-a23	m-a24	m-a25	m-a26	m-a27	m-a28	m-a29	m-a30	m-a31	a23+a24+a25+a26+a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32+a33-5*m	m-a32	m-a33	m-a72	a72
a104	m-a104	4*m-a56-a55-a54-a53-a52-a51-a50	a56+a55+a54+a53+a52+a51+a50-3*m	a5	a6	a7	a8	a9	4*m-a5-a6-a7-a8-a9-a10-a11	a10	a11	m-a34	a34	m-a73	a73
a103	m-a103	a56	m-a56	m-a5	m-a6	m-a7	m-a8	m-a9	a5+a6+a7+a8+a9+a10+a11-3*m	m-a10	m-a11	m-a35	a35	m-a74	a74
a102	m-a102	a55	m-a55	2*m-a20-a21-a22	a20+a21+a22-m	a4-2*a2-a3+2*m	a1-a4+2*a2+a3-m	a3	m-a3	m-a12	a12	m-a36	a36	m-a75	a75
a101	m-a101	a54	m-a54	a22	m-a22	a1	m-a1	a4	m-a4	m-a13	a13	m-a37	a37	m-a76	a76
a100	m-a100	a53	m-a53	a21	m-a21	a2	m-a2	a1-a4+a2	m-a1+a4-a2	m-a14	a14	m-a38	a38	m-a77	a77
a99	m-a99	a52	m-a52	a20	m-a20	a2+a3-a4	a4-a2-a3+m	2*m-a3-a1-a2	a3+a1+a2-m	a12+a13+a14-m	2*m-a12-a13-a14	m-a39	a39	m-a78	a78
a98	m-a98	a51	m-a51	a11-a10+a19	a19	4*m-a11+a10-2*a19-a18-a17-a16-2*a15-a5+a6	a18	a17	a16	a15	a5-a6+a15	m-a40	a40	m-a79	a79
a97	m-a97	a50	m-a50	m-a11+a10-a19	m-a19	a19+a11-a10+a19+a18+a17+a16+2*a15+a5-a6-3*m	m-a18	m-a17	m-a16	m-a15	m-a5+a6-a15	a34+a35+a36+a37+a38+a39+a40-3*m	4*m-a34-a35-a36-a37-a38-a39-a40	m-a80	a80
a96	m-a96	m+a33-a32-a49	m-a49	a32+2*a49+a48+a47+a46+a45+a44+a43+a42+2*a41-a23+a24-5*m-a33	m-a48	m-a47	m-a46	m-a45	m-a44	m-a43	m-a42	m-a41	m+a23-a24-a41	m-a81	a81
a95	m-a95	a32+a49-a33	a49	6*m+a33-a32-2*a49-a48-a47-a46-a45-a44-a43-a42-2*a41+a23-a24	a48	a47	a46	a45	a44	a43	a42	a41	a24+a41-a23	a71+a72+a73+a74+a75+a76+a77+a78+a79+a80+a81-5*m	6*m-a71-a72-a73-a74-a75-a76-a77-a78-a79-a80-a81
m+a70-a69-a94	m-a94	a69-a70+a88+a87+a85+a86+a84+2*a82+a83+2*a94+a93+a92+a91+a90+a89-a57+a58-7*m	m-a93	m-a92	m-a91	m-a90	m-a89	m-a88	m-a87	m-a86	m-a85	m-a84	m-a83	m-a82	m+a57-a58-a82
a69+a94-a70	a94	8*m-a69+a70-a88-a87-a85-a86-a84-2*a82-a83-2*a94-a93-a92-a91-a90-a89+a57-a58	a93	a92	a91	a90	a89	a88	a87	a86	a85	a84	a83	a82	a58+a82-a57

• Details

It is an **algebraic flat-type striped** magic square of order 16 composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×16 and two magic rectangles of order 2×12 embedded with a magic square of order 12. It is again composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×12 and two magic rectangles of order 2×8 embedded with a magic square of order 8. It is again composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×8 and two magic rectangles of order 2×4 embedded with a magic square of order 4. It is again composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 . In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 6m$ and $S_{16 \times 16} := 8m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below two examples:

Example 4.21. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 16 based on Result 3 are given by

16	mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														808	
	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	-285	78	79	808
	35	34	33	32	31	30	29	28	27	26	25	24	23	386	23	22	808
	-593	694	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	199	41	42	21	80	808
	114	-13	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	61	-98	60	59	20	81	808
	113	-12	-30	131	14	15	16	17	18	285	19	20	58	43	19	82	808
	112	-11	65	36	87	86	85	84	83	-184	82	81	57	44	18	83	808
	111	-10	64	37	112	-11	171	-70	12	89	80	21	56	45	17	84	808
	110	-9	63	38	31	70	10	91	13	88	79	22	55	46	16	85	808
	109	-8	62	39	30	71	11	90	8	93	78	23	54	47	15	86	808
	108	-7	61	40	29	72	10	91	169	-68	-35	136	53	48	14	87	808
	107	-6	60	41	29	28	222	27	26	25	24	23	52	49	13	88	808
	106	-5	59	42	72	73	-121	74	75	76	77	78	19	82	12	89	808
	105	-4	44	43	89	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	50	11	90	808
	104	-3	57	58	12	57	56	55	54	53	52	51	50	51	430	-329	808
	-1	-2	748	-1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	9	808
	102	103	-647	102	101	100	99	98	97	96	95	94	93	92	91	92	808
	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808

16	mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														944	
	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	-149	78	79	944
	52	51	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	42	41	40	267	40	39	944
	-491	609	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	301	41	42	38	80	944
	114	4	86	85	84	83	82	81	80	79	78	-183	77	76	37	81	944
	113	5	38	80	14	15	16	17	18	353	19	20	75	43	36	82	944
	112	6	65	53	104	103	102	101	100	-235	99	98	74	44	35	83	944
	111	7	64	54	146	-28	205	-87	12	106	97	21	73	45	34	84	944
	110	8	63	55	31	87	10	108	13	105	96	22	72	46	33	85	944
	109	9	62	56	30	88	11	107	8	110	95	23	71	47	32	86	944
	108	10	61	57	29	89	10	108	203	-85	-52	170	70	48	31	87	944
	107	11	60	58	29	28	290	27	26	25	24	23	69	49	30	88	944
	106	12	59	59	89	90	-172	91	92	93	94	95	-32	150	29	89	944
	105	13	61	60	4	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	67	28	90	944
	104	14	57	58	114	57	56	55	54	53	52	51	50	51	345	-227	944
	16	15	629	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	26	944
	102	103	-511	102	101	100	99	98	97	96	95	94	93	92	91	92	944
	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

(i) *First Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 202, S_{8 \times 8} := 404, S_{12 \times 12} := 606, S_{16 \times 16} := 808$ and $m := 101$.

(ii) *Second Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 236, S_{8 \times 8} := 472, S_{12 \times 12} := 708, S_{16 \times 16} := 944$ and $m := 118$.

4.5.3 Cornered

Result 4. *An algebraic striped cornered magic square of order 16 is given by*

$a_4 - 2a_2 - a_3 + 2m - a_1$	a_1	a_2	$a_2 + a_3 - a_4$	a_5	$m - a_5$	$m - a_{11}$	a_{11}	$m - a_{21}$	a_{21}	$m - a_{35}$	a_{35}	$m - a_{53}$	a_{53}	$m - a_{75}$	a_{75}
$a_1 - a_4 + 2a_2 + a_3 - m$	$m - a_1$	$m - a_2$	$a_4 - a_2 - a_3 + m$	a_6	$m - a_6$	$m - a_{12}$	a_{12}	$m - a_{22}$	a_{22}	$m - a_{36}$	a_{36}	$m - a_{54}$	a_{54}	$m - a_{76}$	a_{76}
a_3	a_4	$a_1 - a_4 + a_2$	$2m - a_3 - a_1 - a_2$	a_7	$m - a_7$	$m - a_{13}$	a_{13}	$m - a_{23}$	a_{23}	$m - a_{37}$	a_{37}	$m - a_{55}$	a_{55}	$m - a_{77}$	a_{77}
$m - a_3$	$m - a_4$	$m - a_1 + a_4 - a_2$	$a_3 + a_1 + a_2 - m$	$2m - a_5 - a_6 - a_7$	$a_5 + a_6 + a_7 - m$	$m - a_{14}$	a_{14}	$m - a_{24}$	a_{24}	$m - a_{38}$	a_{38}	$m - a_{56}$	a_{56}	$m - a_{78}$	a_{78}
$3m - a_5 + a_6 - a_3 - 2a_1 - 2a_2 + a_4 - a_8$	$m - a_8$	$m - a_9$	$a_5 - a_6 + a_3 + 2a_1 + 2a_2 - a_4 + 2a_8 + a_9 + 2a_{10} - 4m$	$m - a_{10}$	$m - a_{10}$	$m - a_{15}$	a_{15}	$m - a_{25}$	a_{25}	$m - a_{39}$	a_{39}	$m - a_{57}$	a_{57}	$m - a_{79}$	a_{79}
$a_5 - a_6 + a_3 + 2a_1 + 2a_2 - a_4 + a_8 - 2m$	a_8	a_9	$5m - a_5 + a_6 - a_3 - 2a_1 - 2a_2 + a_4 - 2a_8 - a_9 - 2a_{10}$	a_{10}	a_{10}	$a_{11} + a_{12} + a_{13} + a_{14} + a_{15} - 2m$	$3m - a_{11} - a_{12} - a_{13} - a_{14} - a_{15}$	$m - a_{26}$	a_{26}	$m - a_{40}$	a_{40}	$m - a_{58}$	a_{58}	$m - a_{80}$	a_{80}
$a_{11} - a_{12} - 2a_7 - 2a_6 + a_3 + 2a_1 + 2a_2 - a_4 + 2a_8 + 2a_9 + 2a_{10} - a_{16} - 2m$	$m - a_{16}$	$m - a_{17}$	$m - a_{18}$	$m - a_{19}$	$2a_{16} - a_{11} + a_{12} + 2a_{20} + a_{19} - 2a_{10} - 2a_9 - 2a_8 + a_4 - a_3 + a_{18} + 2a_7 + a_{17} + 2a_6 - 2a_2 - 2a_1$	$m - a_{20}$	$m - a_{20}$	$m - a_{27}$	a_{27}	$m - a_{41}$	a_{41}	$m - a_{59}$	a_{59}	$m - a_{81}$	a_{81}
$3m - a_{11} + a_{12} + 2a_7 + 2a_6 - a_3 - 2a_1 - 2a_2 + a_4 - 2a_8 - 2a_9 - 2a_{10} + a_{16}$	a_{16}	a_{17}	a_{18}	a_{19}	$m - 2a_{16} + a_{11} - a_{12} - 2a_{20} - a_{19} + 2a_{10} + 2a_9 + 2a_8 - a_4 + a_3 - a_{18} - 2a_7 - a_{17} - 2a_6 + 2a_2 + 2a_1$	a_{20}	a_{20}	$a_{21} + a_{22} + a_{23} + a_{24} + a_{25} + a_{26} + a_{27} - 3m$	$4m - a_{21} - a_{22} - a_{23} - a_{24} - a_{25} - a_{26} - a_{27}$	$m - a_{42}$	a_{42}	$m - a_{60}$	a_{60}	$m - a_{82}$	a_{82}
$m + a_{21} - a_{22} + a_{13} - a_{14} - a_{18} + a_{17} - a_{28}$	$m - a_{28}$	$m - a_{29}$	$m - a_{30}$	$m - a_{31}$	$m - a_{32}$	$m - a_{33}$	$a_{18} - a_{17} - a_{13} + a_{14} + 2a_{34} + a_{33} + a_{32} + a_{31} + a_{30} + a_{29} + 2a_{28} + a_{22} - a_{21} - 4m$	$m - a_{34}$	$m - a_{34}$	$m - a_{43}$	a_{43}	$m - a_{61}$	a_{61}	$m - a_{83}$	a_{83}
$a_{22} - a_{13} + a_{14} + a_{18} - a_{17} + a_{28} - a_{21}$	a_{28}	a_{29}	a_{30}	a_{31}	a_{32}	a_{33}	$5m - a_{18} + a_{17} + a_{13} - a_{14} - 2a_{34} - a_{33} - a_{32} - a_{31} - a_{30} - a_{29} - 2a_{28} - a_{22} + a_{21}$	a_{34}	a_{34}	$a_{35} + a_{36} + a_{37} + a_{38} + a_{39} + a_{40} + a_{41} + a_{42} + a_{43} - 4m$	$5m - a_{35} - a_{36} - a_{37} - a_{38} - a_{39} - a_{40} - a_{41} - a_{42} - a_{43}$	$m - a_{62}$	a_{62}	$m - a_{84}$	a_{84}
$2a_7 + 2a_6 - 2a_8 - 2a_{10} - 2a_9 + 2a_{20} + 2a_{19} + 2a_{16} + 2a_{12} + 2a_{15} + a_{35} + a_{18} + a_{17} + a_{13} + a_{14} - a_3 + a_4 - a_{30} + a_{29} - a_{36} + a_{23} - a_{24} - 3m - a_{44} - 2a_2 - 2a_1$	$m - a_{44}$	$m - a_{45}$	$m - a_{46}$	$m - a_{47}$	$m - a_{48}$	$m - a_{49}$	$m - a_{50}$	$m - a_{51}$	$2a_{44} + 2a_2 + 2a_1 - 2a_7 - 2a_6 + 2a_8 + 2a_{10} + 2a_9 - 2a_{20} - 2a_{19} - 2a_{16} - 2a_{12} - 2a_{15} - a_{35} - a_{18} - a_{17} - a_{13} - a_{14} - a_3 - a_4 + a_{30} - a_{29} + a_{36} + a_{50} + a_{51} + 2a_{52} + a_{45} + a_{46} + a_{47} + a_{48} + a_{49} - a_{23} + a_{24} - m$	$m - a_{52}$	$m - a_{52}$	$m - a_{63}$	a_{63}	$m - a_{85}$	a_{85}
$a_{44} + 2a_2 + 2a_1 - 2a_7 - 2a_6 + 2a_8 + 2a_{10} + 2a_9 - 2a_{20} - 2a_{19} - 2a_{16} - 2a_{12} - 2a_{15} - a_{35} - a_{18} - a_{17} - a_{13} - a_{14} + a_3 - a_4 + a_{30} - a_{29} + a_{36} - a_{23} + a_{24} + 4m$	a_{44}	a_{45}	a_{46}	a_{47}	a_{48}	a_{49}	a_{50}	a_{51}	$2a_7 + 2a_6 - 2a_8 - 2a_{10} - 2a_9 + 2a_{20} + 2a_{19} + 2a_{16} + 2a_{12} + 2a_{15} + a_{35} + a_{18} + a_{17} + a_{13} + a_{14} - a_3 - a_4 - a_{30} + a_{29} - a_{36} - a_{50} - a_{51} - 2a_{52} - a_{45} - a_{46} - a_{47} - a_{48} - a_{49} + a_{23} - a_{24} + 2m - 2a_{44} - 2a_2 - 2a_1$	a_{52}	a_{52}	$a_{53} + a_{54} + a_{55} + a_{56} + a_{57} + a_{58} + a_{59} + a_{60} + a_{61} + a_{62} + a_{63} - 5m$	$6m - a_{53} - a_{54} - a_{55} - a_{56} - a_{57} - a_{58} - a_{59} - a_{60} - a_{61} - a_{62} - a_{63}$	$m - a_{86}$	a_{86}
$m + a_{53} - a_{54} + a_{37} - a_{38} + a_{25} - a_{26} - a_{32} + a_{31} - a_{46} + a_{45} - a_{64}$	$m - a_{64}$	$m - a_{65}$	$m - a_{66}$	$m - a_{67}$	$m - a_{68}$	$m - a_{69}$	$m - a_{70}$	$m - a_{71}$	$m - a_{72}$	$m - a_{73}$	$2a_{64} + a_{65} + a_{66} + a_{67} + a_{68} + a_{69} + a_{70} + a_{72} + 2a_{74} + a_{73} + a_{71} + a_{32} - a_{31} + a_{26} + a_{46} - a_{45} - a_{25} + a_{54} - a_{53} - a_{37} + a_{38} - 6m$	$m - a_{74}$	$m - a_{74}$	$m - a_{87}$	a_{87}
$a_{54} - a_{37} + a_{38} - a_{25} + a_{26} + a_{32} - a_{31} + a_{46} - a_{45} + a_{64} - a_{53}$	a_{64}	a_{65}	a_{66}	a_{67}	a_{68}	a_{69}	a_{70}	a_{71}	a_{72}	a_{73}	$7m - 2a_{64} - a_{65} - a_{66} - a_{67} - a_{68} - a_{69} - a_{70} - a_{72} - 2a_{74} - a_{73} - a_{71} - a_{32} + a_{31} - a_{26} - a_{46} + a_{45} + a_{25} - a_{54} + a_{53} + a_{37} - a_{38}$	a_{74}	a_{74}	$a_{75} + a_{87} + a_{85} + a_{86} + a_{84} + a_{82} + a_{83} + a_{81} + a_{77} + a_{76} + a_{78} + a_{80} + a_{79} - 6m$	$7m - a_{75} - a_{87} - a_{85} - a_{86} - a_{84} - a_{82} - a_{83} - a_{81} - a_{77} - a_{76} - a_{78} - a_{80} - a_{79}$
$a_{24} + 2a_2 + a_{22} + a_{23} + 2a_{27} + a_{65} - a_{66} - a_{88} + a_{75} - a_{17} - a_{13} + a_{14} + 2a_{34} + a_{18} + a_{32} + a_{31} + a_{26} - a_{48} + a_{47} - a_{40} + a_{39} + a_{25} - a_{76} + a_{30} + a_{29} + 2a_{28} + 2a_{33} - a_{56} + a_{55} - 8m$	$m - a_{88}$	$m - a_{89}$	$m - a_{90}$	$m - a_{91}$	$m - a_{92}$	$m - a_{93}$	$m - a_{94}$	$m - a_{95}$	$m - a_{96}$	$m - a_{97}$	$m - a_{98}$	$m - a_{99}$	$a_{99} + a_{98} + a_{97} + a_{96} - a_{65} + a_{66} + 2a_{88} - a_{75} + a_{95} + a_{94} + a_{93} + a_{92} + 2a_{100} + a_{91} + a_{90} + a_{89} + a_{17} + a_{13} - a_{14} - 2a_{34} - a_{18} - a_{32} - a_{31} - a_{26} + a_{48} - a_{47} + a_{40} - a_{39} - a_{25} + a_{76} - a_{30} - a_{29} - 2a_{28} - 2a_{33} + a_{56} - a_{55} + 2m - a_{24} - 2a_{22} - a_{23} - 2a_{27}$	$m - a_{100}$	$m - a_{100}$
$a_{66} + a_{88} - a_{75} + a_{17} + a_{13} - a_{14} - 2a_{34} - a_{18} - a_{32} - a_{31} - a_{26} + a_{48} - a_{47} + a_{40} - a_{39} - a_{25} + a_{76} - a_{30} - a_{29} - 2a_{28} - 2a_{33} + a_{56} - a_{55} + 9m - a_{24} - 2a_{22} - a_{23} - 2a_{27} - a_{65}$	a_{88}	a_{89}	a_{90}	a_{91}	a_{92}	a_{93}	a_{94}	a_{95}	a_{96}	a_{97}	a_{98}	a_{99}	$a_{24} + 2a_{22} + a_{23} + 2a_{27} - a_{99} - a_{98} - a_{97} - a_{96} + a_{65} - a_{66} - 2a_{88} + a_{75} - a_{95} - a_{94} - a_{93} - a_{92} - 2a_{100} - a_{91} - a_{90} - a_{89} - a_{17} - a_{13} + a_{14} + 2a_{34} + a_{18} + a_{32} + a_{31} - a_{26} - a_{48} + a_{47} - a_{40} + a_{39} + a_{25} - a_{76} + a_{30} + a_{29} + 2a_{28} + 2a_{33} - a_{56} + a_{55} - 5m$	a_{100}	a_{100}

• Details

It is an *algebraic cornered striped* magic square of order 16, where the magic squares of order 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 and 14 are at the upper-left corner. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 6m$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 7m$ and $S_{16 \times 16} := 8m$, where m is the width of the *strip*. See below two examples:

Example 4.22. Below are two examples of *algebraic striped* magic square of order 16 based on Result 4 are given by

16	mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				©IJT				704			
	170	1	4	1	13	75	57	31	27	61	-15	103	-69	157	-135	223	704
	-82	87	84	87	16	72	54	34	24	64	-18	106	-72	160	-138	226	704
	7	10	-5	164	19	69	51	37	21	67	-21	109	-75	163	-141	229	704
	81	78	93	-76	128	-40	48	40	18	70	-24	112	-78	166	-144	232	704
	238	66	63	-223	60	60	45	43	15	73	-27	115	-81	169	-147	235	704
	-150	22	25	311	28	28	9	79	12	76	-30	118	-84	172	-150	238	704
	-138	42	39	36	33	280	30	30	9	79	-33	121	-87	175	-153	241	704
	226	46	49	52	55	-192	58	58	226	-138	-36	124	-90	178	-156	244	704
	-3	6	3	0	-3	-6	-9	476	-12	-12	-39	127	-93	181	-159	247	704
	91	82	85	88	91	94	97	-388	100	100	683	-595	-96	184	-162	250	704
	160	-42	-45	-48	-51	-54	-57	-60	-63	920	-66	-66	-99	187	-165	253	704
	-72	130	133	136	139	142	145	148	151	-832	154	154	1452	-1364	-168	256	704
	-117	-102	-105	-108	-111	-114	-117	-120	-123	-126	-129	2152	-132	-132	-171	259	704
	205	190	193	196	199	202	205	208	211	214	217	-2064	220	220	2605	-2517	704
	513	-174	-177	-180	-183	-186	-189	-192	-195	-198	-201	-204	-207	2897	-210	-210	704
	-425	262	265	268	271	274	277	280	283	286	289	292	295	-2809	298	298	704
	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704

16	mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				©IJT		968					
	236	1	4	1	13	108	90	31	60	61	18	103	-36	157	-102	223	968
	-115	120	117	120	16	105	87	34	57	64	15	106	-39	160	-105	226	968
	7	10	-5	230	19	102	84	37	54	67	12	109	-42	163	-108	229	968
	114	111	126	-109	194	-73	81	40	51	70	9	112	-45	166	-111	232	968
	337	99	96	-355	93	93	78	43	48	73	6	115	-48	169	-114	235	968
	-216	22	25	476	28	28	-57	178	45	76	3	118	-51	172	-117	238	968
	-204	75	72	69	66	280	63	63	42	79	0	121	-54	175	-120	241	968
	325	46	49	52	55	-159	58	58	127	-6	-3	124	-57	178	-123	244	968
	30	39	36	33	30	27	24	344	21	21	-6	127	-60	181	-126	247	968
	91	82	85	88	91	94	97	-223	100	100	551	-430	-63	184	-129	250	968
	61	-9	-12	-15	-18	-21	-24	-27	-30	887	-33	-33	-66	187	-132	253	968
	60	130	133	136	139	142	145	148	151	-766	154	154	1287	-1166	-135	256	968
	-84	-69	-72	-75	-78	-81	-84	-87	-90	-93	-96	1954	-99	-99	-138	259	968
	205	190	193	196	199	202	205	208	211	214	217	-1833	220	220	2407	-2286	968
	249	-141	-144	-147	-150	-153	-156	-159	-162	-165	-168	-171	-174	2963	-177	-177	968
	-128	262	265	268	271	274	277	280	283	286	289	292	295	-2842	298	298	968
	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

(i) **First Example:** $S_{4 \times 4} := 172, S_{6 \times 6} := 264, S_{8 \times 8} := 352, S_{10 \times 10} := 440, S_{12 \times 12} := 528, S_{14 \times 14} := 616, S_{16 \times 16} := 704$ and $m := 88$.

(ii) **Second Example:** $S_{4 \times 4} := 242, S_{6 \times 6} := 363, S_{8 \times 8} := 464, S_{10 \times 10} := 585, S_{12 \times 12} := 726, S_{14 \times 14} := 847, S_{16 \times 16} := 968$ and $m := 121$.

For more details refer Taneja [65, 66].

5 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation of Numbers

The magic sum of above magic square is $S_{14 \times 14} := 168$. The internal block is **pandiagonal** magic square of order 12 formed by equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with magic sum $S_{4 \times 4} := 48$

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation of numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares,
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers,
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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- **Different Types of Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares**
- [6] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Rectangles in Construction of Block-Wise Pandiagonal Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-49, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554520>.
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● **Bimagic Squares**

- [11] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Construction of Bimagic Squares: Multiples of Orders 8 and 16.

● **Selfie and Palindromic-Type Magic Squares**

- [12] **Inder J. Taneja**, Selfie Palindromic Magic Squares, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 18(2015), Art. 98, pp. 1-15.
<https://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a98.pdf>.

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● **Perfect Square Sums and Pythagorean Triples Magic Squares**

- [14] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Squares Generated by Pythagorean Triples: Orders 3 to 47, May 28, 2021, pp. 1-119, **Zenodo**, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4837454>.

- [15] **Inder J. Taneja**, Generating Pythagorean Triples and Magic Squares: Orders 3 to 31, **Zenodo**, May 28, 2021, pp. 1-153, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4837491>.

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● Multiple Orders Bordered Magic Squares

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